

ESTABLISHMENT OF A REWARDING PROFESSION: RESPIRATORY THERAPY IN INDIA

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RESEARCH SUPERVISOR'S REPORT

This is to certify that Thesis entitled “**Establishment of a rewarding profession: Respiratory Therapy in India**”, submitted to Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangaluru, Karnataka State, India, by **Jithin K Sreedharan**, for the award of degree of **Doctor of Philosophy in Allied Health Sciences, Respiratory Therapy** is a record of bonafide research work carried out by him under my supervision. The Thesis has reached the standard of the regulations for the degree and it has not been previously formed the basis for the award of any degree, diploma, associateship, fellowship or any other similar title to the candidate or any other person(s).

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DECLARATION

This thesis, “**Establishment of a rewarding profession: Respiratory Therapy in India**”, is the result of my own study carried out under the supervision of **DR. Udaykumar Rao, MBBS, MD**, Professor, Srinivas University, Mangaluru and has not been submitted earlier to any University for any degree, Diploma or any other similar title. This Thesis is free from any kind of plagiarism.

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SYNOPSIS

ESTABLISHMENT OF A REWARDING PROFESSION: RESPIRATORY THERAPY IN INDIA

1.0 INTRODUCTION

During the last few decades, though India has made much progress in the area of public health care delivery system, still it is placed at a lower rank among the member countries of WHO as far as healthcare performance is concerned. India is struggling with constant increase in population associated with heavy burden of diseases including various epidemics and emerging new infections. Since life expectancy has been enhanced during last decades, life style and non-communicable diseases are on the rise and high rate of maternal and child deaths.

The WHO report stated that there is acute shortage of doctors, nurses and midwives in India. The average nurse-patient ratio across the country is around 1:40, which is very much lower to that of Indian Nursing Council (INC) norms. INC recommends a nurse-to-patient ratio of 1:4. Similarly, there is doctor-patient population ratio of 1: 1,674 and it is ranked at the position of 67th among developing nations. India is supposed to achieve the doctor population ratio of 1:1000 as recommended by 'High Level Expert Group (HLEG) for Universal Health Coverage' constituted by the Planning Commission of India.

Under these conditions, there is the need to strengthen the areas of preventive medicine, early diagnosis and patient management to make the health services affordable for every citizen at an affordable cost. Hence, there is a need to overcome workforce shortages by involving allied health personnel (AHP) in the main stream of patient care, thereby the primary care can be made available

to the rural and under-privileged areas by paramedical staff and AHPs. An AHP is a suitable alternative in areas where a medical physician is not available especially in providing primary health services, by this means reducing the dependency on medical graduates; health services can reach a vast majority of our population with minimal investment.

Respiratory Therapy (RT) is an emerging allied healthcare specialty in India, giving new dimensions to solve the challenges being faced by health services providing communities across the country. Respiratory Therapist's provide a range of patient care services like curative, preventive, diagnostic, rehabilitative, monitoring & therapeutic services coupled with research and development. RT in comparison to other health-care discipline is a young profession and thus many people, including other health-care disciplines, may not be sure what a Respiratory Therapist (RT) is or what they can do. The general public does not usually find out about them until they are in a hospital or receiving home oxygen.

RT as a profession is described as “an allied health-care specialist who, under a physician's medical direction and supervision, plans and implements a variety of therapeutic and diagnostic procedures for patients suffering from a wide range of heart and lung disorders. They combine technical skills with scientific information for the benefit of the patients they serve.”

Respiratory therapists also work in our country and bringing their expertise to:

- Homecare, Long-term care
- Asthma, emphysema, cystic fibrosis and other pulmonology and rehabilitative clinics
- Medical education & Teaching
- Critical and emergency care
- Research & Clinical Simulation

- Diagnostic clinics and sleep disorder labs
- Transport, pre-hospital care and out of hospital care.
- Medical equipment sales and service, research and development

Like other professionals in medicine, practicing RT's have an inherent responsibility to keep abreast of their field by reading current literature and attending professional meetings. Their major goal must be the well-being of the patient and this requires them to strive to provide the best services possible by keeping up-to-date of new developments. For most people, breathing is as easy and natural as blinking. However, for millions of Indian citizens, breathing is a struggle. They might be accident victims, premature babies with immature lungs, heart attack and stroke patients, or people who live with asthma and emphysema. When it comes to their care, a respiratory therapists' will likely play a vital role on the healthcare team. In our country RT's generally work in larger hospitals, usually those are having 50 or more beds, and work with the entire medical team in all areas of the hospital.

This broad research included the preparedness of new graduate respiratory therapists (RT) to enter the workforce, supervised clinical experiences in respiratory therapy education, minimum degree requirements for entry into professional practice. Also addressed the student's perspectives about their career growth. Although job satisfaction has a strong association with respiratory therapists' performance, the job satisfaction of Indian respiratory therapists (RTs) has not previously been examined. A cross sectional survey was conducted to measure the job satisfaction level among Indian RTs and to identify the occupational and personal characteristic factors that influence the job satisfaction, and career prospects.

2.0 LITERATURE SURVEY

The American Association for Respiratory Care (AARC) released a study that identified the shortage of respiratory therapists in the United States (USA). The study projected that based on 111,706 therapists working in the USA and a report of 6,500 full time equivalent vacancies the overall vacancy rate was approximately 6%. Three quarters of the therapists working in the USA are employed by acute care hospitals. The shortage in the USA parallels that being experienced in Canada and makes recruitment from the USA.

The need to direct efforts and resources towards the retention of respiratory therapists was highlighted by a study undertaken by Stoller, Orens, and Kester in 2001. Key hospital personnel were surveyed to determine the rate of staff turnover as well as the costs associated with orientation and training of new staff members. The three most important reasons identified by respiratory therapists for leaving a job were to seek more job satisfaction, to seek higher salary, and lack of opportunities for job advancement.

Factors, cited by Sobel et al, as affecting recruitment and retention included; inadequate wages, lack of funding and incentives for continuing education, lack of career opportunities, workload, shift work, lack of support for families of shift workers such as provision of day care, and the grouping of respiratory therapists with technical staff rather than professional staff when negotiating contracts. Concern regarding the program management structure was also expressed.

In a study, Rawlins (1987) surveyed 71 respiratory therapists in three hospitals to determine factors affecting job satisfaction and turnover. The best predictors of attrition were stress with the job role, financial stress, and dissatisfaction with supervision and co-workers. Lack of respect from medical staff was also identified as stressful.

A study published by Shevade et al (2019) in her cross-sectional observations study identified that out of 223 respondents, 52% were females and 48% males, with mean age of 26.4 ± 5.4 years with clinical experience of 3.6 ± 4.2 years. 70% had a BS degree, 18% had an MS degree, 2% Ph.D. and 10% certificate, RT diploma or other educational backgrounds. 93% participants worked as RT or any job role that required RT knowledge while 7% either quit or changed careers. Although they may have multiple job roles, 75.7% work as a staff respiratory therapist in hospitals. RTs in India spend 51% of their time in adult intensive care unit (ICU), 7% in an emergency room, 7% pulmonary function testing, 5% paediatric ICU 5% neonatal ICU, 5% university, 5% clinic and 15% other areas.

A recent review by Sreedharan JK. et. al. also described the current educational programs in India and need for professional regulation in the country. He also briefly mentioned about the countries needs for the respiratory therapy professionals and recommends a road map to outline the respiratory therapy profession in India.

3.0 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

In India, precise studies are not available to estimate respiratory therapy work force and related information to help proper area-specific public health interventions. Reliable data on scope of practice, students' perspectives, educational and minimum standards resource are scarce in general; they are almost non-existent in the country other than the south part. Paucity of this adequate data makes the understanding of the profession and its situation more complex. Keeping the above points in view, this paper will discuss about the health care human resource burden with focus on respiratory therapy as an important allied health care specialization.

4.0 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

By considering the concepts of **Establishment of a rewarding profession: Respiratory Therapy in India**, objectives set forth for the study may be broadly be stated as below.

- This study aims to measure the status of respiratory therapy work force in India, in terms of supply, distribution, educational background, and demographic distribution.
- This study aims to identify the employment setting, nature of work, compensations and job satisfaction, and future opportunities of Respiratory Therapists.
- Identify Career progression path from entry level to senior management level and entry-level employment opportunities and demand-supply gaps.
- This study is trying to explore the rationale behind the global migration of Qualified Respiratory Therapists from India.
- This study aims to identify student enrolments, attrition, student diversity and availability of faculties in educational institutions.

The study included the following components:

- ✓ Key informant interviews with HODs, Supervisors and entry-level staffs of respiratory therapy departments.
- ✓ A state-wide survey of HODs, and staffs of respiratory therapy departments.
- ✓ Key informant interviews with Deans, HODs, Faculties and students of respiratory therapy educational programs.
- ✓ Comparative analyses of respiratory therapy education in terms of competencies and curricular content.
- ✓ A review of academic literature.

5.0 HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

Based on the above objectives, following Hypothesis have been formulated:

- H (1): There is an association between Demographic variables and job satisfaction among Respiratory Therapists.
- H (2): There is an association between perceptions and career progression among Respiratory Therapists.
- H (3): There is an association between perceptions of the students and demographic variables.
- H (4): A significant relationship exists between educational background and RT job satisfaction
- H (5): No significant relationship exists between age, educational background, and job satisfaction
- H (6): A significant relationship exists between years practicing as an RT and RT job satisfaction.
- H (7): A significant relationship exists between recognition for RT and RT job satisfaction
- H (8): A significant relationship exists between the place they work and RT job satisfaction
- H (9): A significant relationship exists between the place they work and RT job satisfaction
- H (10): A significant relationship exists between the type of hospital RTs work and, the of ICU beds they have and RT job satisfaction
- H (11): A significant relationship exists between the remuneration the RT Receive and RT's job satisfaction
- H (12): A significant relationship exists between the hours RTs work and RT job satisfaction
- H (13): A significant relationship exists between the number of RTs work in the Hospital and RT job satisfaction
- H (14): A significant relationship exists between the RTs job satisfaction and plan for leaving the profession.

6.0 METHODOLOGY

This study has a descriptive, cross-sectional non-experimental design. This study is looking into the data collected from various sources including databases, specialist organisations' reports, articles, books, workshop reports, government documents and earlier research done about the respiratory therapy workforce in India. Validated and structured questionnaires are developed for conducting the survey. After getting the approval of the institutional review board, the cross-sectional surveys are distributed to the practicing and non-practicing respiratory therapists, respiratory students and head of the departments of RT programs across the country. The surveys were conducted using an electronic platform (survey monkey/google forms) questionnaire. Staff participants were asked about their education, experience, current job, responsibilities and how frequently they utilized the competencies learned during training etc and also their career perspectives. Descriptive statistics was performed using SPSS latest and available version, and logistic regression was performed with the assistance of statistical units. Consent was taken prior to the surveys.

7.0 SAMPLING

We have considered Universities listed by the University Grants Commission, a statutory organization of the Government of India which coordinates, determines and maintains standards of teaching, examination and research in the university Education in the year 2021-2022 for collecting the student's perception on career progression and evaluation of learning resources survey (SURVEY-1).

We have selected 13 universities based on the following criteria:

- The universities are listed by University Grants Commission (UGC).
- The universities must have class on the main campus.

Based on the above criteria, the following Universities are selected:

- ✓ All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Rishikesh.

- ✓ Amrita Viswavidyapeetham University, Coimbatore.
- ✓ Chettinadu University, Chennai.
- ✓ Jagadguru Sri Shivarathreeshwara (JSS) University, Mysore.
- ✓ Manipal University, Manipal.
- ✓ MGR University, Chennai.
- ✓ NITTE University, Mangalore.
- ✓ Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences, Bangalore.
- ✓ Saveetha University, Chennai.
- ✓ Sri Ramachandra Institute of Higher Education and Research (SRMC), Chennai.
- ✓ Srinivas University Mangalore.
- ✓ Symbiosis International University, Pune.
- ✓ Yenepoya University, Mangalore.

The data is collected from 904 respondents from the universities across India. The entire population is considered for the study. Hence the sampling technique is not applicable. The second survey included 388 working Respiratory Therapists, graduated from Indian universities for assessing the perceptions, job satisfaction and its impact on career progression. The results were included for further analysis. The above discussed variables are hypothesized in the proposed model and examined the relationship by using descriptive statistics, Karl Pearson correlation coefficients, Fisher's exact test, and backward regression analysis. The Chi-square test and Fishers Exact test is used to know the relationship between variables. The response was collected for each component by using a 5-point Likert scale (1=Strongly Disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Neutral, 4= Agree and 5= Strongly Agree). The reliability and validity of the questionnaire are examined Cronbach alpha coefficient test.

8.0 CONTRIBUTION OF THE RESEARCH TO SOCIETY

This novel data will be useful to the profession, notably for academic programs that must meet the need for a more highly prepared and skilled workforce. The findings will emphasize that viability of the profession in the current health-care environment calls for the evolution of a more autonomous RT who can be reimbursed for services and obtain salaries and other professional growth that are competitive with other health professions. The results will also empower the future policy makers and leaders in the respiratory therapy profession to in the regularization and standardization process. The data will also have an insight to the perspectives of the students who are entering to the profession. This study will have information's to the current and future directions of the respiratory care profession in India. The policy makers may identify the increasing the scope of practice of the RT, advocating for competitive work environment with other allied health professions, and promoting a higher academic standard for the profession.

9.0 CHAPTER SCHEME

This study is organized in six chapters. The description of each chapter is presented below:

Chapter 1: Introduction

This chapter introduce the Respiratory Therapy profession, history of the profession and how it was started in India, 25 years before. This chapter also introduces the work profile of a respiratory therapist as well as the general competencies of a qualified RT.

Chapter 2: Review of Literature

This section is presenting the literature review undertaken by the researcher. The review of literature was carried out in 5 major themes. **Respiratory Disorders**, section briefly presents the prevalence and the significance of Respiratory Care in the present era in the Indian perspective.

Section 2 is themed as **Global Prevalence**, where a detailed literature search regarding the respiratory diseases, and the burden it is causing to the healthcare domain was carried out and presenting how it impacted globally. Section 3 is presenting **Pulmonary Rehabilitation** as an important component in the management of chronic respiratory management and the present literature supporting its significance. Section 4 deals with the core aspects of **Respiratory Therapy** and its evolution in the literature. It elaborates the key incidents in the development of the profession over the past 60 years globally. Section 5 is introducing the literature available regarding the evolution of **Respiratory Therapy in India** since 1995. It also discusses the current evidence available regarding the practice pattern of respiratory therapists, demographic characteristics and educational background of present RT workforce in India.

Chapter 3: Methodology

The first chapter deals with the research design of the study. The design includes an introduction, statement of the problem, objectives of the study, and hypotheses of the study, data sample and methodology, sampling, result of reliability test, validation of structured questionnaire. The first section of this chapter presents the overall research approach followed by a section on the population and research setting. Other sections will feature the examination of the research instruments, data collection procedures, and data analysis.

Chapter 4: Results

This chapter discusses the association Socio-demographic variables, students' perceptions and satisfaction of learning resources, their career prospects. Furthermore, it discusses the challenges of present RT workforce in the country along with their demographic variables and nature of work.

Chapter 5: Discussion

This chapter also includes the discussion of the mean score and the impact of work life balance on job satisfaction, Organizational commitment, Family satisfaction, and employee performance. It discuss in detail the views of the students studying RT program in different universities across the country. The results of descriptive statistics are also discussed.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

In this chapter, we sum up our study by discussing the major findings of the third, fourth, and fifth chapters. The conclusions are drawn based on findings and suggestions.

10.0 REFERENCES

This includes the references made in the study derived from secondary data that helps in identifying, formulating and solving the research problem.

11.0 ANNEXURE

It incorporates a survey confined for the study, factors name, reliability statistics, the discriminant scores of the given information, drafted Questionnaire and values for the given set of information.

12.0 FUTURE SCOPE OF RESEARCH

Even though the sampling size is acceptable, further studies can be done by increasing the sample size by including central universities, private universities and deemed to be universities, categorically to see the change in the results of the study. This will improve the universality of the findings. The researchers can consider expanding this study in other allied healthcare specialities as a sampling frame to study the student satisfaction, and working group for understanding the level of satisfaction.

CONTENTS

1.0	INTRODUCTION.....	20
1.1	RESEARCH QUESTIONS/HYPOTHESIS.....	22
2.0	SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF LITERATURE.....	24
2.2	GLOBAL PREVALENCE.....	26
2.3	PULMONARY REHABILITATION	29
2.4	RESPIRATORY THERAPY AND THERAPISTS	31
2.5	RESPIRATORY THERAPY IN INDIA.....	32
3.0	METHODOLOGY	35
3.1	RESEARCH QUESTIONS.....	35
3.2	MIXED METHOD DESIGN FOR SCALE DEVELOPMENT.....	36
3.3	POPULATION AND SAMPLING.	37
3.4	DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENTS AND PROCEDURES.....	38
3.5	THE USE OF SEMI-STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS.....	39
3.6	THE RATIONALE FOR USING THEMATIC ANALYSIS.....	40
3.7	STEP 3 - MIXING VALIDATION: CONTENT-BASED VALIDITY (FACE VALIDITY) OF SCALE ITEMS (ZHOU, 2019).....	43
3.8	PHASE II: QUANTITATIVE PHASE.....	44
3.9	SAMPLING PROCEDURE.....	45
3.10	STUDY DESIGN	45
3.11	ETHICAL CLEARANCE AND INFORMED CONSENT.....	45
3.11.1	PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECT	46
3.11.2	INFORMED CONSENT AND INVITATION LETTER	46
3.12	STUDY POPULATION	46
3.13	QUESTIONNAIRE TOOL	47
3.14	STATISTICS.....	48
4.0	RESULTS	49
4.1	DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF A STRUCTURED QUESTIONNAIRE TO ASSESS THE PERCEPTION OF RESPIRATORY THERAPY STUDENTS TOWARDS THEIR FUTURE CAREER PROSPECTS ..	49
4.2	STUDENTS' PERCEPTION TOWARD RESPIRATORY THERAPY CAREER AND THEIR LEVEL OF SATISFACTION WITH THE LEARNING RESOURCES	55
4.3	DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF QUESTIONNAIRE FOR ASSESSING PERCEPTIONS, JOB SATISFACTION AND ITS IMPACT ON CAREER PROGRESSION AMONG RESPIRATORY THERAPISTS IN INDIA. 69	
4.4.	PERCEPTIONS, JOB SATISFACTION AND ITS IMPACT ON CAREER PROGRESSION AMONG RESPIRATORY THERAPISTS IN INDIA	77
5.0	DISCUSSION.....	95
6.0	CONCLUSION	103

8.0 REFERENCES.....	106
ANNEXURE: QUESTIONNAIRE.....	117
PLAGIARISM REPORT.....	ERROR! BOOKMARK NOT DEFINED.
CURRICULUM VITAE.....	ERROR! BOOKMARK NOT DEFINED.
PUBLICATIONS	126

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The global prevalence of respiratory disorders are increasing due to multiple factors such as improper lifestyle, decrease in air quality and increase in particulate matter pollution as a result of increase in the number of industries, automobiles, etc. [1]. Especially in India, respiratory disorders have become one of the leading causes of increasing morbidity and mortality. For example, number of deaths due to lower respiratory tract infection was highest in India when compared to any other country in the world [2]. And, COPD remain as the second leading cause of NCD-related deaths in India. Increase in the incidence of respiratory disorders in India is attributed to factors like change in lifestyle, industrialisation and socio-economic status [3]. Studies show that 50% of patients who visit a primary care physician in India is for the management of respiratory symptoms and about half of those patients visit specifically for chronic respiratory diseases [4].

In a densely populated developing country like India, with an estimated 100 million people being affected with chronic respiratory diseases [5]. The direct and indirect cost implications due to respiratory disorders is huge. A huge gap also exists between the number of patients and the number of healthcare professionals like physicians and nurses, for the management of these patients. As a result, there are higher chances of under-diagnosis and inadequate management of chronic respiratory diseases [6]. An appropriate solution to reduce this huge burden would be in providing a comprehensive healthcare solution and appropriate pulmonary rehabilitation from the grass root level all the way to super speciality hospitals through a multidisciplinary team. The scarcity of a qualified doctor demands an adequately trained and skilled middle management personnel who could liaison between doctor and patients with respiratory conditions. Such models have been found to be

beneficial in many parts of the world in dealing with various respiratory disorders such as COPD, interstitial lung disease, pulmonary hypertension, bronchiectasis and lung cancer.

The role of respiratory therapists (RTs) in particular is important as they provide an end-to-end care to patients, right from providing supportive therapy during their hospital stay all the way to providing rehabilitation post-hospitalisation. RTs work in both acute and chronic clinical settings and are employed as clinical specialists, as healthcare researchers and as faculties at the Universities and Colleges. This is believed to ensure reduction in the duration of hospital stay and also recurrent hospital visits of the patients [7]. Respiratory therapy as a profession originated in the year 1943 and the field has grown leaps & bounds ever since and it has grown to such an extent that it has become an essential part of healthcare with over 134,000 registered RTs working in the United states alone [8, 9]. The success of the respiratory therapy field along with increasing need for the RTs has prompted other nations as well to adopt the profession, by employing RTs and offering various training programs as well [9].

In India, the respiratory therapy profession was introduced around 1995. Respiratory Care programs are delivered in universities across the country and each university having their own unique nomenclature for their respiratory therapy programs and degree courses, such as Respiratory care technology, respiratory therapy, medical technology-RT, allied health science in respiratory therapy and respiratory care technician. Unlike in the United States and many other western and Middle Eastern countries, the role of RTs in India is currently limited. Though the respiratory care profession was established 25 years back in India, its application in the country is still an emerging concept [10]. RTs have clinical competencies in executing various procedures, effecting handling equipment, diagnosis and management of respiratory conditions and patient care. However, a study done in India on RTs showed that they ‘infrequently recommended diagnostic procedures, used evidence-based

principles, initiated patient and family education or administered home care or pulmonary rehabilitation' [4]. The authors attributed the behaviour to the domination of healthcare system by the doctors, lack of a structured allied health council and RTs are in fact, RTs are not given the autonomy to make recommendations to the patients [11]. Even knowledge regarding the very existence of various respiratory therapies in India is found to be limited among common people [12]. Though respiratory therapists play an integral role in the multi-disciplinary healthcare teams, their importance has not come into the limelight up until the recent COVID-19 pandemic, where they acted as frontline COVID warriors saving many lives. Respiratory therapists played a significant role in COVID and also post-COVID management, playing a vital role in reducing morbidity and mortality to a greater extent.

Respiratory therapy in India is a relatively new and fast-growing speciality. Being an emerging field, it has a lot of scope to serve millions of people affected with both communicable and non-communicable respiratory conditions. The need for respiratory therapists would grow exponentially in the near future as their importance as an integral part of the multidisciplinary team is being realised and recognised, not just in the emergency care, but also in the primary care setting [13]. Respiratory therapy could thus be a very rewarding profession as it would help reduce the morbidity and improve overall Quality of Life (QoL) in millions of patients who are affected with communicable and non-communicable diseases across the country.

1.1 Research Questions/Hypothesis

In order to achieve the research goals, the study will seek to answer the following questions.

RQ1. To assess the respiratory therapy students' perspectives towards carrier and satisfaction about the learning resources

RQ2. To assess the perceptions, job satisfaction and its impact on career progression among respiratory therapists in India

Years	Event
1995	Four-year BSc in Respiratory Care courses started MCOAHS - Manipal, Karnataka SRMC - Chennai, Tamil Nadu
1996	Two-year Diploma in Respiratory Care CMC - Vellore, Tamil Nadu
1997	Two-year Diploma in Respiratory Care started NIMS - Hyderabad, Andhra Pradesh MediCiti Hospital - Hyderabad, Andhra Pradesh
1998	Establishing ARCI in Hyderabad It is the first official professional association for practicing RTs in India
1999	Three-year BSc in RCT under RGUHS - Karnataka SJIC - Bangalore
2002	Diploma in Respiratory Care KMCH - Coimbatore Under Dr. MGR Medical University, Tamil Nadu
2006	Manipal College of Allied Health Sciences - Manipal, Karnataka Starts the first Master's Program in Respiratory Care
2006	BSc in Respiratory Care in the state of Maharashtra SIU - Pune
2010	Bachelor's and Master's Program in Respiratory Care Amrita Viswavidyapeetham University - AIMS, Kochi - Kerala
2011	ARCI becomes IARC and formally registered under the Karnataka society act
2012	Launching the Prestigious IJRC The official scientific publication of IARC, under the umbrella of Manipal University

MCOAHS: Manipal College of Allied Health Sciences, SRMC: Sri Ramachandra Medical College, CMC: Christian Medical College, NIMS: NIZAM'S Institute of Medical Sciences, ARCI: Association for Respiratory Care-India, RTs: Respiratory therapists, RGUHS: Rajiv Gandhi University of Health Sciences, SJIC: Sri Jayadeva Institute of Cardiology, KMCH - Kovai Medical Center Hospital, SIU: Symbiosis International University, AIMS: Amrita Institute of Medical Sciences, IARC: Indian Association of Respiratory Care, IJRC: Indian Journal of Respiratory Care, BSc: Bachelor of Science, RCT: Respiratory care technology

Figure 1.1 Important events in the evolution of respiratory therapy profession in India
(Image extracted with permission from Reference 42)

CHAPTER 2

2.0 SCIENTIFIC REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Respiratory Disorders

Respiratory lung diseases are diseases of the airway tract and other structures of the lung. Chronic respiratory diseases such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), asthma and occupational lung diseases is on the rise [14]. The morbidity and mortality due to respiratory lung diseases are increasing worldwide at a staggering rate with four million people dying prematurely due to the conditions [14]. The WHO Global Alliance against chronic respiratory diseases was established with the objective of reducing the global burden of the chronic respiratory diseases. The WHO global alliance report mentions that the major risk factors include exposure to effects of smoke from domestic cooking and industries, effects of outdoor and indoor air pollution, both active and passive smoking^[4]. Smoking was the leading risk factor to increase both morbidity and mortality that occurs due to chronic respiratory disease. Smoking causes prolonged and exaggerated inflammatory response in the lungs which persists for many years and contributes majorly to the aetiology of COPD. An estimated 544.9 million individuals had chronic respiratory disease with the global prevalence of 7.1%, The prevalence rate was higher in high income countries at 10-11%, when compared to south Asia (5.5%) and sub-Saharan Africa (5.1%). COPD was the leading cause of mortality due to chronic respiratory diseases, followed by asthma. Over 180,000 deaths worldwide are attributed to asthma, however, the morbidity associated with asthma is much greater than mortality [15]. The prevalence of asthma is much higher in urban than in rural areas due to environmental exposure and on the contrary, its prevalence is much higher in low-income countries

due to lack of access to quality medical care [16]. Lung cancer is one of the most common malignancies across the globe and is the most preventable as well.

Lower respiratory tract infections are often characterised by conditions such as pneumonia or bronchiolitis, due to pathogens such as Haemophilus influenza type b (Hib), Streptococcus pneumoniae, influenza and respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), with global prevalence and increased risk of morbidity and mortality. Nearly 2.38 million deaths are being reported as a result of lower respiratory tract infections in the year 2016, making it the sixth leading cause of mortality across ages and the also the leading cause of mortality in children younger than 5 years [17]. The common risk factors attributed to lower respiratory infections includes lack of adequate nutrition, clean fuel to cook, sanitation, vaccination and other related immuno-compromised conditions. The number of deaths due to lower respiratory tract infections reduced by 13.1% between the year 2000 and 2016. The Global Action Plan for Pneumonia and Diarrhoea (GAPPD) was formed by WHO and UNICEF with a vision to prevent and treat lower respiratory tract infection, and reduce mortality rates to as low as three deaths per 1000 individuals by 2025, and reduce the incidence of lower respiratory tract infection to 75% of the 2010 levels [2]. The mortality rate was highest in sub-Saharan Africa, south and Southeast Asia when compared to high income countries. Though vaccination and antibiotic usage could possibly prevent 30.2% of lower respiratory tract infection related deaths, there is a serious threat that the universal use of antibiotics might lead to antimicrobial resistance [18]. Both indoor and outdoor pollutants are key components to air pollution induced lower respiratory tract infection which are inversely proportional in view of the socio-economic demography of a country. For example, as a country develops socio-economically, the indoor air pollution reduces greatly due to replacement of biofuels for cooking to natural gas and electricity, whereas there is increase in the

outdoor pollution due to particulate matter pollution. Indoor pollution is much higher than outdoor pollution in the low economic countries when compared to the high-income countries [2].

Respiratory infections due to virus are major public health challenge, especially in densely populated areas and countries, wherein the spread of the microorganism spreads from one person to the other directly through small or large droplets while coughing, sneezing and talking, or indirectly due to contact with contaminated surfaces [19]. The elderly people (aged 65 years and above) are documented to be at increased risk of respiratory viral diseases [20]. Alongside, lower respiratory tract infection and chronic respiratory diseases such as COPD, asthma, etc., there is increase in the emergence of severe epidemics and pandemics in the past two decades related to lungs such as severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS), Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS), influenza A (H1N1) and most recently, COVID-19. This could possibly be attributed to any or all of the above factors such as reduced air quality, reduced immunity, increase in elderly population due to increased life expectancy and increase in the population density.

2.2 Global Prevalence

The five major conditions that contribute to the global respiratory burden includes acute respiratory infections, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and asthma, tuberculosis and lung cancer [15]. Among all the chronic respiratory diseases, COPD alone contributes to almost 50% of all the respiratory conditions. COPD leads to disability and reduces quality of life, accounting to 69% of overall life years lost due to disability [21]. COPD is also among the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in the world and is estimated as the sixth leading cause of death [22]. The global prevalence of COPD is estimated to be 11.37% and the economic burden of COPD in Europe varies across the continent, with per-patient cost of work productivity loss being highest in Germany (Euros 5,735) and lowest in Greece (Euro 998) [23].

The prevalence of COPD and asthma varies across the countries. Almoamary et al., (2021) states that the prevalence of asthma and COPD in Saudi Arabia had shown an increasing trend between 1990 and 2000 [24]. The prevalence rate of asthma and lifetime wheeze in Saudi Arabia was 14.3% and 16.5% respectively. The overall prevalence of asthma in children range between 8% and 25%, as shown through several studies in the past three decades. The increase in prevalence could be attributed to lifestyle and urbanisation, tobacco usage, sandstorms, exposure to environmental pollutants including indoor and outdoor allergens in the past three decades. The author also attributes the increase in prevalence to increase in awareness of the respiratory condition among healthcare workers and population in general, allowing better diagnosis of asthma.

In the United States (US), 16.4 million adults or 6.6% adults above 18 years of age suffer from COPD in the year 2018. The prevalence varied across the states, with 4% adults in Hawaii and 15.3% adults in West Virginia were affected with COPD [13]. The United States COPD National Action Plan (US-CNAP) has been formed with five major objectives (i) to empower people with COPD, along with their families and caregivers (ii) improve the quality of healthcare by improving prevention, diagnosis and management of COPD (iii) collect and analyse COPD-related public health data (iv) improved research (v) translate national policies and recommendations into public health strategies [25, 26].

In Canada, an estimated 2.74 million individuals suffer from asthma which leads to death of nearly 250 Canadians annually. The economic burden is mostly due to uncontrolled asthma that increases both healthcare utilisations, medical costs and also loss of productivity [27, 28]. And, COPD remains as the most common respiratory condition along with asthma. Four major components for asthma care was suggested by the National Asthma Education Program (NAEP), namely, patient education, control of environmental factors that could possibly increase

exacerbations, pharmacologic therapy and appropriate objective measure of asthma and its severity [28]. COPD is the fourth major reason for mortality in Canada and a nationwide drive to reduce the major risk factor- exposure to tobacco smoke, both active and passive, would help reduce the incidence and risk of COPD [29].

In Portugal, management of chronic respiratory disorders has been given priority since 2000, and Portugal is one of the top countries with lowest hospitalisation due to asthma and COPD. The estimated prevalence of asthma in children and adults are 11% and 5.2% respectively, with prevalence of COPD in adults above 40 years being 14.2% [30, 31].

In Latin America, 10-20% of population is affected with COPD and more than 30% is affected with asthma in some parts of Latin America. Several programs are successfully running across Latin America in countries such as Brazil, Uruguay, Argentina and Mexico in order to bring down the prevalence.

In the African country of Mozambique, the burden of communicable diseases is generally high. However, since the year 2000, an increase in the non-communicable diseases (NCDs) is being documented in Mozambique with the prevalence of asthma in children being as high as 13.3%. The major constraint reported in the management of respiratory disorders in the country is limited access to the health exercises and higher priority being given to the communicable diseases than NCDs like COPD and asthma [32].

The Asian country of Vietnam has an estimated 7.2 million people affected with either asthma or COPD. To tackle this nationwide increase in prevalence, several steps were taken between the year 2000 and 2007 in collaboration with many national and international organizations including establishment of Asthma and COPD Outpatient Care Units (ACOCUs). A network of over 161

ACOCUs were established since 2000 with an aim to improve quality of care across the country [32].

In India, the number of deaths due to lower respiratory tract infection was highest when compared to any other country in the world, as specified both in Global Burden of Disease (GBD) in 2015 (1,40, 649) and in 2016 (1,67,500) [2]. An estimated 17 million people suffer from respiratory disorders in India [12]. The disability-adjusted life-years (DALYs) caused due to chronic respiratory disorders is significantly high in India, with 32% of global DALYs reported to occur in India [33]. Similarly, the estimated prevalence of COPD in India was 7.4% with prevalence being higher in male than female. The prevalence was higher in the Northern regions of the country and a relatively higher prevalence in the urban than rural regions [23]. COPD is the second leading cause of NCD-related deaths in India. Tobacco smoking, indoor and outdoor air pollution, age, gender and socio-economic status are the risk factors attributed to increased prevalence of COPD in the Indian context [3]. COPD and asthma, also accounts for 75.6% and 20% of respiratory DALYs respectively, which is 1.7 and 2.4 times higher than the global average [33].

2.3 Pulmonary Rehabilitation

Pulmonary rehabilitation is an important component in the management of chronic respiratory diseases; however, it is rarely being practiced by the RTs or by the physicians [34]. The direct and indirect cost implications due to respiratory illnesses are huge. The COPD exacerbations possibly requires an admission in hospitals and costs somewhere over USD \$40,000 for every hospitalization [35]. Lack of a structured and comprehensive COPD care for the patients alone is speculated to be around \$44 billion per year in the United States [36]. The solution for reducing this huge cost burden would be appropriate comprehensive management of the patients and is to be started from the time of admission to post-discharge rehabilitation. Pulmonary rehabilitation (PR) which comprises of

education and tailor-made exercises, is to be delivered by multidisciplinary teams to get optimum benefits through reducing symptoms, improving exercise tolerance and quality of life. PR is recommended for various respiratory disorders such as COPD, interstitial lung disease, pulmonary hypertension, bronchiectasis and lung cancer. Role of respiratory therapists in this multidisciplinary team is crucial as they provide supportive therapy, thereby reducing hospital stay. They also ensure better recovery during the follow-up and help reduce possible recurrent hospital visits of the patients [7]. The application of pulmonary rehabilitation is universal especially in the developed countries.

The pulmonary rehabilitation (PR) services in the United Kingdom (UK) has multidisciplinary teams comprising mostly occupational therapists, physiotherapists, nurses and dietitians. However, the role of respiratory therapists in UK is limited unlike other countries like Saudi Arabia [37]. According to the 2018 PR audit in the UK, there was remarkable differences in care across and within UK due to multiple variables such as location, referral criteria, the healthcare team and attendance rate of the patients [38].

The PR programs were launched in Saudi Arabia as early as 2001, however its application was not widely utilised. The feasibility of successfully running a PR program at the outpatient department was first tested later in the year 2008 at King Abdulaziz Medical City in patients with chronic lung diseases [24]. More recently, the Saudi Thoracic Society (STS) has a set guideline recommending exercise, self-management, education and nutritional support as important components, for a duration of PR to be 6-12 weeks of supervised sessions to deliver an effective pulmonary rehabilitation (PR) program. Respiratory therapists play a major role as a part of the multidisciplinary team in Saudi Arabia in delivering effective care to patients [37].

2.4 Respiratory Therapy and Therapists

Ever since the introduction of Wagner's Chronic care model, there is radical transformation in the health care. With increasing prevalence of the NCDs, the focus in healthcare has slowly started to shift from the regular conventional medical model of focusing on diagnosing and treating acute conditions to a more holistic model focusing on long term prevention and management aspects of the chronic or potentially incurable conditions. Many key elements were identified by Wagner in improving patient related outcomes in chronic NCDs, which includes as using appropriate guidelines and evidence-based therapies in the management of chronic conditions, promote self-management of disease conditions and to improve community resources to ensure support to the individual. The most important of which is to establish a multi-disciplinary team in collaboration among clinical practitioners to ensure better disease management, rather than delivering health service through a single care provider [13]. Respiratory therapy or respiratory care is an allied health profession (AHP) which deals primarily with prevention, diagnosis and management of cardiopulmonary conditions. Respiratory therapists have diverse roles and responsibilities on various aspects of healthcare such as primary care, casualty, paediatrics, rehabilitation, homecare, etc. and provide the much needed respiratory care to the patients. Respiratory therapists bring a 'unique skill set' in the management of respiratory disorders [13].

The evolution of respiratory therapists (RTs) in respiratory care is remarkable since its introduction as a distinct speciality in the year 1940 in the United States (US). Ever since its evolution, qualified RTs handle both critical and emergency care modalities like pulmonary diagnostics, mechanical ventilation, pulmonary rehabilitation and home care. With increase in the sophistication of medical care and increasing number of respiratory related disorders such as COPD, SARS, MERS and COVID-19 there is greater demand and need for highly skilled RTs who emphasizes on evidence-

based practice. Because, respiratory care provided by suitably qualified and skilled. RTs are documented to reduce the cost of care, improved patient related outcomes with lower ICU and hospital stays [39]. Improved patient related outcomes is attributed to increase in the application of evidence-based medicine. Importance of evidence-based medicine (EBM) is emphasized in all aspects of medicine. According to Tweed et al (2007), EBM was introduced way back in early 1900's to provide a structured framework and methodological approach towards enabling physicians to deliver effective clinical care to the patients, through available evidences from relevant research and previous clinical practise. EBM evolved conceptually into evidence-based practice encompassing and including other relevant domains of medicine such as nursing, physiotherapy and other allied health professionals. The dissemination of these medical knowledge has increased exponentially with rapid emergence of internet and online electronic databases. Respiratory therapists are expected to be up-to-date in knowledge and in par with the rest of the medical fraternity following EBM and deliver utmost care being part of the multidisciplinary team.

2.5 Respiratory Therapy in India

India is a densely populated country with over 1.38 billion people. Respiratory diseases are the second leading cause of morbidity and mortality in India. Mortality due to lower respiratory tract is highest in India [2], and with over 17 million people suffering from respiratory disorders [12], RTs would play a significant role in the prevention, management and rehabilitation due to respiratory disorders. As a profession, respiratory therapy in India has come a long way since it was believed to be established in the year 1995 [11] by Dr. Ramkumar Venkateswaran, an anaesthesiologist from Manipal University. In 1995, when Dr. Ramkumar came back to India along with few other eminent doctors after completing the international fellowships from the American Association of Respiratory Care (AARC) from the Loma Linda University (California, USA), he designed and started the first

formal degree program in respiratory therapy in India [40, 41]. Around the same time, pulmonologists from various institutions started with similar programs as well at the certificate level. Though many challenges such as lack of adequate educational resources, simulation centres, poor faculty retention policy and workspace expansion [42], an estimated 1,000 graduates have successfully completed the program as of 2019 [43]. Having said that, respiratory therapy in India is still taking its baby steps and has not yet received the due recognition either from the fellow medical professional or from the Government of India [11].

Shevade et al., (2021) demonstrated that the RTs always or often performed most of the listed competencies, but hesitate to recommend further diagnostic procedures, initiate or conduct patient/family education or administer homecare by themselves. The authors attribute this particular behaviour is due to the healthcare system in India, which is mostly driven by the doctors, and RTs are believed to not have the autonomy to make recommendations towards diagnostic tests or initiate patient education or counselling [4].

Evidence-based protocols and evidence-based practice are widely recommended for RTs across the globe and same is applicable in the Indian scenario as well [44]. With diverse clinical exposure, teaching institutions and increased prevalence of respiratory disease in India, there is a huge potential to enhance research among RTs. The research need not necessarily be experimental studies, and the publications could be as simple as case reports, case series, audits, review articles or surveys which promotes evidence-based practice among the RTs and the respiratory therapy students [40, 45].

As far as future career prospects are concerned, most government institutes do not have a regular post for RTs and even in private sectors, RTs are recruited for lower pay scales [4]. However, respiratory therapy is being widely applied in various field of healthcare, with numerous institutions

offering RT training programs across the country. With increase in demand due to multiple factors such as increased population, industrialisation and pollution and novel innovations in the field of medicine has enabled a quantum leap in the need for respiratory therapists in India. RTs have started assuming new roles and responsibilities, taking larger supportive roles alongside traditional nursing functions [42]. And, respiratory therapy could thus probably be a rewarding career in the near future in India. In the given scenario, we intend to understand the perception of (i) the respiratory therapy students towards their future career prospects and (ii) the current curriculum they are undergoing in their respiratory therapy program, through a structured and validated questionnaire.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Respiratory therapists (RTs) play a vital role in healthcare. Therefore, identifying the competencies for RTs is important for determining the criteria for training them. The purpose of the current study is to develop a feasible, reliable and valid scale for measuring students' perspectives towards carrier progression and perception towards satisfaction in India.

The current chapter features the presentation of the research methodology to be used in the proposed study. According to Creswell (2007), the appropriate research methodology should be informed primarily by the research questions and the delimitation of the study [46]. Accordingly, the current study will follow a mixed-method approach that utilizes both qualitative and quantitative methods to provide a holistic investigation. The first section of this chapter presents the overall research approach followed by a section on the population and research setting. Other sections will feature the examination of the research instruments, data collection procedures, and data analysis.

3.1 Research Questions

In order to achieve the research goals outlined above, the study will seek to answer the following questions.

RQ1. To assess the respiratory therapy students' perspectives towards carrier and satisfaction about the learning resources

RQ2. To assess the perceptions, job satisfaction and its impact on career progression among respiratory therapists in India

3.2 Mixed Method Design for Scale Development

There are different methods available for developing a scale such as a 13-steps approach (Smolleck, 2006), [47] and a 9-steps approach [48]. The proposed study will utilize a 5-step mixed-method approach that develops descriptive qualitative research to inform a quantitative examination of the research questions, therefore, the conceptual framework recommended by Zhou (2019) for scale development using mixed methods will be followed [49].

This framework has five steps:

1. Qualitative exploration: Scale construct and Qualitative validation: Content-based validity
2. Mixing phase: Converting qualitative data to scale items.
3. Mixing validation: Content-based validity (face validity) of scale items.
4. Quantitative phase: Administering the new scale
5. Quantitative validation: Construct based validity (Zhou, 2019, p.43 - 44) [49].

Figure 3.1 The conceptual framework based on Zhou's model.

3.2.1 Phase I: Qualitative Phase

The qualitative phase comprises the first three steps of Zhou's (2019) model [49] and seeks to respond to the question: What are the main perspectives towards career progression and perception of job satisfaction of respiratory therapists as identified by two groups from India:

Group 1: Respiratory therapist/faculties working in the hospital/College setting (Junior/Senior/Heads of the department).

Group 2: Graduate and post graduate students of Respiratory Therapy at all level (studying in a medical college/university).

Step 1 - Qualitative exploration: Scale construct and Qualitative validation: Content-based validity [49].

Scale construction heavily depends on qualitative research because this exercise not only delivers the required information for item writing but also offers the basis for the validity of the content of the items. I will employ inductive approach by questioning a sample of respondents to offer descriptions of their feelings/perceptions about the respiratory therapist in their colleges [50]. I will utilize semi-structured interviews to develop items for measuring perspectives of respiratory therapist in healthcare systems of the India.

3.3 Population and Sampling.

The target population will be from healthcare and educational organizations in India. Five top leaders (CEO / Dean / Vice Dean), five senior therapists (Head of the Clinical Departments in a Hospital setting and Head of Departments in a college setting), and five employees (working in hospital or college) in the field of health care and medical education will be interviewed based on a semi structured interview guide.

Bryman and Bell (2011) define sampling as the process for choosing a sample which is a subset of the population in which research will be conducted [51]. The study will adopt techniques that save time and reduce cost constraints due to the large scope of the research. In this case, non-probabilistic techniques including simple modified random and purposeful sampling techniques will be employed. The sampling techniques will be critical for the sample selection based on a predetermined criterion.

The inclusion criteria for the respondents comprises the following:

- (i) The participant must be 18 years and above
- (ii) Student who enrolled for formal respiratory therapy degree OR post graduate degree course in one of the UGC recognized university.
- (iii) Work in an educational or healthcare organization with distinct management levels
- (iv) Work in an educational or healthcare organization in India

The sampling approach will involve using a simple modified random sampling to select the representative sample of the population. The random sampling technique allows the possibility for all participants to appear in the research. Then, purposeful sampling within the identified random sample will be done based on the predetermined selection criteria. Care will be taken to recruit participants from different regions of India, to ensure, diversity in the respondents.

3.4 Data collection instruments and procedures

Due to the use of mixed methods research, triangulation of data collection is essential to improve the trustworthiness of the qualitative data [51]. In Phase 1, interviews will be conducted from three groups and the data will consist of responses from semi-structured interviews conducted by the primary investigator with three groups namely, top leaders, senior therapist and students. The

interviews will be transcribed and analysed using an emergent thematic analysis approach focusing on the competencies that respondents discuss.

3.5 The use of semi-structured interviews.

The interview is “a method of data collection in which one person (an interviewer) asks questions to another person (a respondent)” [52]. Interviews are considered to be one of the most frequently used techniques for data collection [53]. There are three different types of interviews – unstructured where questions emerge based on the setting, semi-structured wherein a set of open-ended predetermined questions are used, and finally, structured interviews where a group of closed questions are employed [54].

Interviews are usually used as the first step for generating an initial pool of items for scale development [55]. Interviews fall in the domain of inductive methods where qualitative information about a construct is acquired from the selected panel of experts or from defined target population [56]. Researchers often consult with group of experts for revising the items in terms of clarity and comprehension. In this study, semi structured interviews with a group of experts will be conducted during the first step (step 1) of qualitative exploration. Such a structured discussion with experts in specific areas facilitate not only the process of item generation but also the method of validation including content validity and face validity [57].

Notably, some of the shortcomings include that the process is time-consuming, and labour-intensive. Apart from that, setting up the interview logistics, preparation of questions, recording and transcribing, and textual analysis require considerable effort and time. However, semi-structured interviews are suitable for the tasks where the open-ended question needs follow-up inquiries for clarification. Furthermore, the use of individual interviews rather than focus groups is more suitable given the participants’ cultural sensitivities. Participants may not be comfortable or candid about

respiratory therapist skills in a focus group setting where there is inherently different social status [58].

Step 2 - Mixing phase: Converting qualitative data to scale items (Zhou, 2019).

Qualitative data analysis is commonly reliant on the process of interpretation, [59] that is achieved through the researcher reviewing the text and determining the meaning that is conveyed by the speaker. There are multiple ways of performing a textual qualitative analysis [60] and thematic analysis is applied in this study

3.6 The rationale for using thematic analysis.

Thematic Analysis (TA) has over the years been utilized by researchers as a method in various qualitative research designs [61]. TA is considered more appropriate for finding a relationship between different variables through the process of coding and observing patterns, especially if the study involves interviews with multiple participants from diverse environments. TA also provides opportunity to present the data in form that closely mirrors the meaning expressed by the speaker or respondent.

TA is a systematic technique used to identify, organize, and provide facts regarding patterns of themes or meaning across a dataset. TA aggregates meanings and does not focus on idiosyncratic and unique events or associate themes with a single data point (Lawless & Chen, 2019). In this study, the purpose is to identify the perspectives towards carrier and job satisfaction of respiratory therapist from individuals holding different hierarchical positions in the healthcare system. Thus, the data will be analysed with the intention of identifying those themes and patterns that address the research question.

Figure 3.2 | Levels of coding

3.6.1 Open coding.

The open coding stage begins with reading the transcribed data which is presented in a textual format. It is recommended that more than one researcher should be involved in coding process to enhance the credibility of the coding process [62]. Hence, in this study, two researchers will read the transcripts of the interviews line by line and assign category of codes to different chunks of text after comparing and conceptualizing [63]. The number of codes identified can significantly vary as useful codes are determined for the purposes of understanding of the phenomenon under study. This process facilitates identification of vital categories in the form of codes and the newly emerging codes will be continuously compared with the already existing codes to provide higher level of abstraction. Both the researchers should arrive at acceptable level of agreement ranging from 75% to 90% before proceeding with axial coding [64].

3.6.2 Axial coding.

After the open coding stage is finished, the researcher will obtain numerous codes and begins with axial coding stage. The aim of axial coding is to “to determine which [codes] in the research are the dominant ones and which are the less important ones ... [and to] reorganize the data set: synonyms are crossed out; redundant codes are removed and the best representative codes are selected” [65].

Axial coding also helps to create a conceptual framework. During this stage the researcher will ascertain the evidences which illustrate a pattern and assign the relevant codes in different manner, bringing out categories and sometimes to sub-categories. In this study, the researcher will code for the characteristics, qualities, and competencies that the participants identify as important for effective respiratory care therapist.

3.6.3 Selective coding.

Following the stage of axial coding, the researcher will proceed with the process of selective coding and identify the sub-themes and classify them into central themes around which the analysis and interpretation of the research question will be based [66]. The themes that are identified will be used for item generation for measuring characteristics and competencies required for successful respiratory therapist in the health care sector. Minimum of four to six items will be generated for each construct. It is also anticipated that usually, half of the original items are retained in the final scale, and therefore it is recommended to generate as many as twice the number expected items in the final scale, to be included in the survey questionnaire. After completion of this stage, a framework for survey questionnaire for respiratory professional competencies will be developed, that can be utilized in Phase 2 of the study for the development of a scale to measure the same.

3.7 Step 3 - Mixing validation: Content-based validity (face validity) of scale items (Zhou, 2019).

Validity refers to the ability of an instrument to measure what it was designed to measure. According to Cooper and Schindler (2014), validity is a primary measure of the quality of the measuring instruments in the research [67]. It evaluates the degree that the questionnaire measures what it was intended to measure. Face validity is a subjective judgment on the operationalization of a construct.

The content validity of the measuring instrument is the degree to which the items in the constructs are able to establish the concepts being researched as noted by McDaniel and Gates (2013) [68]. Content validity has a subjective judgment from the experts regarding the appropriateness of the measurements, thus used to obtain adequate reporting regarding the research questions and the control of the research. A good content validity should have instruments that are a representative sample of the research concept [67].

The face validity and content validity will be assessed by sending the newly developed items to five experts from each group (Group 1, 2 & 3) and asking for their response about the applicability of the given characteristics. The items will be presented as a binominal scale with two options, 'Yes' or 'No' / 'Agree' or 'Disagree' to denote whether the corresponding item can be included in the scale or not.

To determine which items to retain, a consensus approach will be used. This process of consensus development consists of discussion between the researcher and the selected individuals to reach at a general agreement. In this case, it is crucial for four expert raters (80%) from each of the three groups to agree that the item reflects the competency applicable to respiratory professional of health care sector in India.

3.8 Phase II: Quantitative Phase

After completing the first three steps of Zhou's (2019) conceptual framework using a qualitative approach for generation of items for the scale development, the final two steps for reliability and construct validity will be implemented using a quantitative approach.

3.8.1 Item generation

A series of informal focus group meetings with various Respiratory care specialities were conducted, and the discussions were verbatim transcribed in a word document. Themes were produced through thematic analysis by qualitative experts at the institution, which eventually became the items of SQ, which included four primary domains relevant to the vital parts of the respiratory care profession, namely perception, satisfaction, curriculum, and suggestions. A few questions were also added to obtain demographic information and other relevant information.

3.8.2 Content validation

Content validation was carried out by 4 internal and 4 external experts by Lawshe method [69]. Teachers and respiratory therapists were chosen as internal and external experts, and they were judiciously applying respiratory care concepts they had learned from within and outside our university, respectively. Acceptance for inclusion in the SQ is based on the agreement of at least five out of eight experts. Expert input and suggestions provided for significant developments, resulting in the construction of a more comprehensive SQ. The resulting SQ had 40 closed-ended questions ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 3 (strongly agree) on a Likert scale, as well as open-ended questions about facilitating factors, hindering factors, and suggestions. The SQ was scored using a Likert scale, which is a widely accepted and extensively used psychometric measure in educational research [70].

3.9 Sampling procedure

We have used a convenience sampling process, reaching potential participants through my personal and work affiliations and their extended networks. Survey distributed electronically via email and social media invitation. We have obtained permission to send out survey invitations via email to all medical colleges in India, that were part of the network of colleges in my work organization, a total of more than 25 universities and affiliated medical colleges. Because this organization works with medical colleges in every state, across rural, suburban, and urban areas, and with all socioeconomic levels, we anticipated to achieve a representative sample of respiratory therapist. We sent an email to the heads of institutions, usually principals or other administrators, at these colleges and requested that they send the survey invitation to faculties in their colleges and hospitals.

3.10 Study design

This cross-sectional study used an online survey to evaluate perception and satisfaction of RT students toward career prospects and learning resources in Medical universities of India between June and September 2020.

3.11 Ethical clearance and informed consent

Institutional Ethics Clearance was obtained from the host institution before the participants were recruited (*Ref: SUEC 2020/001 Dated 02.01.2020*). Informant consent also obtained for all the students and faculties before commencement of the project. Participants had the right to withdraw from the study at any time.

3.11.1 Protection of Human Subject

Institutional review board of the **Srinivas University** reviewed and approved the research proposal. Confidentiality is crucial in data collection; hence the researcher informed the participants that the data which they provided were secured. The rights of the participants were reserved and protected. Respondents to this survey remained anonymous

3.11.2 Informed Consent and Invitation Letter

All participants in this study received an invitation letter in addition to the survey. The invitation letter was displayed on the first page of the survey. Informed consent was provided to participants before the questionnaire began. Participants were asked to consent before moving on to the questionnaire; if they refused, the survey would end before any further steps could be performed.

3.12 Study population

3.12.1 For Students survey:

Data was collected from the 904 RT students currently enrolled in RT programs at any medical college in India. The questionnaire was circulated through email and WhatsApp to all the participants. Students were informed that the purpose of the survey; was to assess their perception regarding career prospects and satisfaction with the available learning resources. Informed consent was obtained from all the respondents.

3.12.2 For Respiratory Therapists (RTs) survey:

Data was collected from the 338 RT faculties currently working at any medical college in India. The structured questionnaire was circulated through email and WhatsApp to all the faculties. Faculties were informed that the purpose of the survey; was to assess their perceptions, job satisfaction and its impact on career progression among Respiratory Therapists in India.

3.13 Questionnaire tool

We have used structured questionnaire (SQ) to assess the perception towards future carrier and satisfaction from the RT students. A series of informal focus group meetings were conducted with various Respiratory care professionals, and the discussions were verbatim transcribed in a word document. Themes were produced through thematic analysis by qualitative experts at the institution, which eventually became the items of SQ.

3.13.1 For Students survey

SQ for the student survey consisting of a total of 27 items, which is a combination of four subscale: Perception (4 items), satisfaction (13 items), suggestions (4 items), and curriculum (5 items). We have done the validation for the above-mentioned scale (Explanatory (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA)) and found satisfactory fit for the RT students. Cronbach alpha values for the four items domains ranged from 0.74 to 0.92. The total Cronbach alpha measure was 0.92, which is considered satisfactory. The SQ was scored using a Likert scale (ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 3 (strongly agree), a widely accepted and extensively used psychometric measure in educational research.

3.13.2 For Faculty survey

SQ for the faculty survey containing of the total of 36 items, which is a combination of three subscale: Perception (17 items), Attitude (4 items), and satisfaction (15 items). We have done the validation for the above-mentioned scale Explanatory (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA)) and found satisfactory fit for the RT faculties with above three model. Cronbach alpha values for the three items domains ranged from 0.89 to 0.94. The total Cronbach alpha measure was 0.94, which is considered satisfactory. The SQ was scored using a Likert scale (ranging from 1 (strongly disagree)

to 3 (strongly agree), a widely accepted and extensively used psychometric measure in educational research.

3.14 Statistics

Duplicate, impossible, and invalid data were reviewed first before proceeding on to the primary analyses. After that, a histogram was used to check normality, and a box plot was used to check outliers for factor analysis. There were no outliers found, and the distribution was close to normal. First, the calibration sample was subjected to an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) utilizing principal component analysis to explore the factor structure in each of the four components [71]. The field specialists predetermined the individual factors and underlying components.

R statistical version 4.0.2 was used to evaluate global goodness of fit model indices. The goodness-of-fit index (GFI), comparative fit index (CFI), root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), approximate goodness of fit indices (AGFI), normed fit index (NFI), and standardized root mean square residuals are among these indices (SRMR). The degree of variance and covariance are combined in the GFI to represent how well the model fits the sets of observed data.

CFI is used to compare the null model to the proposed model's fits. The data is acceptable if the value is greater than 0.90. The RMSEA also describes how well the model quantitatively fits the observable data. A value of less than 0.05 is regarded to be a good fit. SRMR is defined as a closed fit, with values less than .05 indicating a good fit and values between .05 and .08 indicating an appropriate fit. The NFI scale is 0 to 1, with higher values indicating better fit [72, 73]. CFAs were performed using the Lavaan package of R version 3.1.2 [74].

CHAPTER 4

4.0 RESULTS

4.1 Development and validation of a structured questionnaire to assess the perception of respiratory therapy students towards their future career prospects

Nine hundred and four students were included in the analysis after the exclusion of thirty-one students as an invalid case or not willing to participate in the survey. Majority of the students (n=446, 48%) were 20-22 years old and over half of the students were female (60%). Both EFA and CFA were then performed to assess the validity of the tool.

4.1.1 Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

EFA was conducted on the Likert scale items for each factor of the questionnaires. According to the predefined models, the perception factor contained 16 items (P1–P16), the satisfaction factor contained 13 items (S1–S13), curriculum factor contains 6 items (C1–C6) and the suggestion factor contained 5 items (SU1–SU5). Normality assessment usually rejects if the ratio of skewness is $> \pm 1$ and/or kurtosis is $> \pm 2$ [75]. The items' distribution deviated from the normality on above mentioned range removed from the model (Table: 4.2.1).

The Kaiser-Meyer-Oklin (KMO) is a measure that provides an approach to comparing the zero-order correlations to the partial correlations between pairs of variables [76]. The KMO in the study model was 0.90; Kaiser (1974) stated that if the KMO is > 0.50 , it is acceptable. The closer the KMO is to 1, the better the correlations between the pairs of variables that can be explained by the other variables [77].

The results of the EFAs for perception showed that 12 items did not load (factor loading less than 0.30) on the factor well; P1 to P9, P11, P12 and P 16. For the curriculum factor, C5 item and suggestion factor, SU1 and SU6 were not loaded well. Therefore, they were sequentially trimmed from the model. The modified model on perception comprised of P10 and P13-P15, satisfaction comprised S1-S13, Curriculum contains C1-C4 & C6 and Suggestion factor contains SU2-SU5 and accounted for 43.7% of the total variance (Figure:1).

Table 4.1.1: - Descriptive Statistics for characteristics Scale Items (n = 904)

Descriptive Statistics								
Items	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis	
P1	904	1	3	2.95	0.261	-5.381	30.852	
P2	904	1	3	2.93	0.304	-4.658	22.571	
P3	904	1	3	2.91	0.351	-3.99	16.079	
P4	904	1	3	2.76	0.523	-2.117	3.563	
P5	904	1	3	2.82	0.443	-2.402	5.197	
P6	904	1	3	2.23	0.945	-0.478	-1.712	
P7	904	1	3	2.47	0.848	-1.068	-0.755	
P8	904	1	3	2.14	0.903	-0.285	-1.716	
P9	904	1	3	2.59	0.759	-1.462	0.336	
P10	904	1	3	2.08	0.933	-0.157	-1.834	
P11	904	1	5	3.7	1.01	-0.374	-0.391	
P12	904	1	5	3.89	0.965	-0.611	-0.231	
P13	904	1	5	4.34	0.892	-1.271	0.985	
P14	904	1	5	3.1	1.192	0.052	-0.863	
P15	904	1	5	3.89	1.081	-0.724	-0.255	
P16	904	1	5	4.24	0.988	-1.156	0.599	
S1	904	1	5	3.81	1.076	-0.813	0.138	
S2	904	1	5	3.85	1.038	-0.849	0.318	

S3	904	1	5	4.12	0.859	-0.954	0.98	
S4	904	1	5	3.93	1.004	-0.838	0.189	
S5	904	1	5	3.98	0.932	-0.797	0.342	
S6	904	1	5	4.1	0.954	-1.136	1.164	
S7	904	1	5	3.99	0.949	-0.952	0.813	
S8	904	1	5	4.02	0.977	-0.998	0.767	
S9	904	1	5	4.11	0.93	-1.064	1.022	
S10	904	1	5	4.01	0.918	-0.829	0.554	
S11	904	1	5	4.01	0.956	-0.834	0.311	
S12	904	1	5	4.07	0.947	-1.003	0.881	
S13	904	1	5	3.94	1.049	-0.961	0.555	
C1	904	1	5	3.75	0.958	-0.592	0.081	
C2	904	1	5	3.89	0.846	-0.578	0.413	
C3	904	1	5	4.15	0.788	-0.869	1.124	
C4	904	1	5	4	0.854	-0.696	0.408	
C5	904	1	5	3.73	0.991	-0.45	-0.226	
C6	904	1	5	3.99	0.9	-0.663	0.052	
SU1	904	1	5	4.25	0.807	-1.036	1.144	
SU2	904	1	5	4.29	0.791	-0.957	0.697	
SU3	904	1	5	3.5	1.14	-0.354	-0.653	
SU4	904	1	5	3.37	1.168	-0.169	-0.886	
SU5	904	1	5	3.73	1.047	-0.445	-0.376	
KMO and Bartlett's Test								
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.							.902	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity						Approx. Chi-Square	4995.17	
						df	351	
						Sig.	.0001	

Table 4.1.2: Factor Loadings and Communalities

Items	Factor loadings	Communalities
.P10	0.868	0.324
.P13	0.433	0.178
.P14	1.035	0.173
.P15	0.702	0.320
.P16	0.526	0.344
.S1	0.66	0.298
.S2	0.563	0.315
.S3	0.37	0.473
.S4	0.387	0.519
.S5	0.435	0.550
.S6	0.298	0.666
.S7	0.298	0.544
.S8	0.422	0.663
.S9	0.289	0.667
.S10	0.243	0.591
.S11	0.35	0.647
.S12	0.351	0.689
.S13	0.363	0.645
.C1	0.318	0.616
.C2	0.214	0.674
.C3	0.337	0.589
.C4	0.422	0.599
.C6	0.556	0.438
.SU2	0.554	0.369
.SU3	0.606	0.347
.SU4	0.277	0.293
.SU5	0.462	0.472

As shown in Table 4.1.1, the factor loadings for all the items ranged from 0.30 to 1.03, and the internal consistency was Cronbach $\alpha = 0.85$. Table 2 shows the loading of the 27 items on the four factors and the accounted cumulative variance with the entire sample (>64%).

Figure: 4.1.1 Scree plot for SQ

Table 4.1.3: Confirmatory Factor Analysis Process for scale

χ^2	RMSEA	TLI	CFI	GFI	χ^2 / df	P value
198	0.06	0.97	0.94	0.92	4.9	0.01

Pearson’s correlation coefficients were calculated to explore the inter-relationships between factors [Table 4.1.2]. The measurement model fit using CFA is shown in Figure 4.1.1. The model fit the data adequately with a good GFI (0.92), TLI (0.97) and RMSEA (0.06). The raw χ^2 is 198 and χ^2 / df is 4.9 with p-value < 0.01 (Table: 4.1.3).

Figure: 4.1.2 SEM results of the confirmatory factor analysis

Table 4.1.4 : Validity and Reliability Measures

	AVE	CR	MSV
Perception	0.76	0.90	0.19
Satisfaction	0.79	0.84	0.24
Curriculum	0.68	0.86	0.32
Suggestions	0.72	0.82	0.22

The AVE of the constructs in the study were measured and compared to the inter-factor correlations [78]. Preliminary evidence of convergent validity was determined when the AVE of each construct was higher than its correlation with other constructs. While discriminant validity of the competency scale was preliminarily determined by assessing the Maximum Shared Variance (MSV), and found to be lower than the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for all of the constructs in the scale [79]. Convergent and Discriminant validities results are available in Table 4.1.4.

4.2 Students' perception toward Respiratory Therapy career and their level of satisfaction with the learning resources

Of the 904 RT students, 554 were female (59%) and 349 were male (37%). The age range included ranged from 18 yrs to above 30 years. Around 380 (41%) respondents were between 18-20 yrs old, 446 (48%) were between 20-22 yrs, 53 (5.7%) were between 23-25 yrs and 11 (1.2 %) was below 18 yrs old. The RT students were from bachelor degree, a total of 856 respondents (92%), Diploma 2 (0.2%) and Master degree 46 (4.9%). Responses were obtained from Internship 163 (17%), first year 218 (23%), second year 280 (30%), and third year 243 (26%) employees. Only very few (76 [8.1%]) of the family member/realities of students belongs to RT field. Table 4.2.1 and Figure 4.2.1 provides further details on the demographic characteristics of the participants.

Among the respondents, majority were Bachelor's students (92%). Around 59% of the respondents were female, with average family income being less than one lakh per annum in 60% respondents. Around 89% of the respondents were new to the respiratory therapy field with no family member or relative being in the field before. And, 90% of the respondents had plans of moving abroad for job opportunities (Table 4.2.1).

In total, 69% of respondents either agree or strongly agree that the nature of their work is physically and emotionally challenging (Table 4.2.2). Gender specific difference was observed only in this particular response, as 82.9% female agreed or strongly agreed that the work is physically and emotionally challenging, with a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) between genders (Table 4.2.3). The respondents also perceived that the RTs are not adequately recognised, as 83% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that RTs are not adequately recognised for their contributions, with no gender specific difference in response (Table 4.2.1).

Table: 4.2.1 Demographical characteristics of the study participants

Characteristic	N = 904(%)
Type of Degree	
Bachelor	856 (92%)
Master	46 (4.9%)
Diploma	2 (0.2%)
Current Academic Year	
Second year	280 (30%)
Third year	243 (26%)
First year	218 (23%)
Internship	163 (17%)
Age (yrs)	
20-22	446 (48%)
18-20	380 (41%)
23-25	53 (5.7%)
25-30	11 (1.2%)
Less than 18	11 (1.2%)
Above 30	3 (0.3%)

Gender	
Female	554 (59%)
Male	349 (37%)
Other	1 (0.1%)
Marital status	
Unmarried	875 (94%)
Prefer not to say	16 (1.7%)
Married	13 (1.4%)
Annual Income	
< 1 Lakh	539 (860%)
1-3 Lakh	250 (27%)
4-6 Lakh	72 (7.7%)
> 6 Lakh	43 (4.6%)
Type of Family	
Nuclear Family	693 (74%)
Joint Family	199 (21%)
Extended Family	12 (1.3%)
Family member or a relative working as RT or related field	
No	828 (92%)
Yes	76 (8%)
Enrolment to the program	
Fully supported by the family	662 (71%)
Educational loan from the bank	176 (19%)
Self-funded	50 (5.3%)
Scholarship funded	16 (1.7%)
Do you have plan for moving abroad for Job	
Yes	809 (90%)
No	95 (10%)

Satisfaction regarding the learning resources were high, as 67% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that their institute matches with international standards of respiratory therapy, physical facilities like classroom, furnishing, computers, etc. (69%) and quality education tools (72%). When it comes to faculty members, 79% agreed or strongly agreed that their faculties have excellent academic, practical and professional skills, with 76% agreeing or strongly agreeing that there exists good interaction and rapport between the students & teaching faculty. Around 76%

respondents agreed or strongly agreed that they gain excellent benefits from the clinical and practical trainings. Regarding the safety and security of the clinical training site, 80% of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed it to be safe and secure (Table 4.2.4, Table 4.2.5).

Figure: 4.2.1 Responded Students Mapping

Regarding the suggestions provided by the respondents, 85% either agreed or strongly agreed that career-counselling need to be provided by the University and 86% emphasized on the importance and urgent need for establishing a regulatory body for RT, across the genders with no difference across the genders (Table 4.2.6, Table 4.2.7).

Table: 4.2.2 Students response for perception towards career prospects and learning resources

Perception	Characteristic	N = 904
News stories about the Respiratory Therapists shortage	Yes	442 (49%)
	No	313 (35%)
	Don't know	149 (16%)
Not enough new graduates to fill the increasing number of jobs/demand	Neutral	299 (33%)
	Agree	281 (31%)
	Strongly Agree	233 (26%)
	Disagree	70 (7.7%)
	Strongly Disagree	21 (2.3%)
Work is physically and emotionally challenging	Agree	349 (39%)
	Strongly Agree	274 (30%)
	Neutral	199 (22%)
	Disagree	72 (8.0%)
	Strongly Disagree	10 (1.1%)
In India; RTs are not recognized enough for their contributions	Strongly Agree	511 (57%)
	Agree	235 (26%)
	Neutral	117 (13%)
	Disagree	35 (3.9%)
	Strongly Disagree	6 (0.7%)
Other careers are more attractive, so RTs change their profession.	Neutral	289 (32%)
	Disagree	212 (23%)
	Agree	177 (20%)
	Strongly Agree	145 (16%)
	Strongly Disagree	81 (9.0%)

Table: 4.2.3 Students response for perception about career prospects and learning resources

Based on the gender Perception	Characteristic	Overall, N = 904	Female, N = 554	Male, N = 349	p-value
News stories about the Respiratory Therapists shortage	Don't know	149 (16%)	91 (16%)	58 (17%)	0.055
	No	313 (35%)	209 (38%)	104 (30%)	
	Yes	442 (49%)	254 (46%)	187 (54%)	
Not enough new graduates to fill the increasing number of jobs/demand	Agree	281 (31%)	184 (33%)	96 (28%)	0.5
	Disagree	70 (7.7%)	46 (8.3%)	24 (6.9%)	
	Neutral	299 (33%)	188 (34%)	111 (32%)	
	Strongly Agree	233 (26%)	122 (22%)	111 (32%)	
	Strongly Disagree	21 (2.3%)	14 (2.5%)	7 (2.0%)	
Work is physically and emotionally challenging	Agree	349 (39%)	282(50.9%)	130 (37%)	0.025
	Disagree	72 (8.0%)	47(8.5%)	38 (11%)	
	Neutral	199 (22%)	46 (8.3%)	77 (22%)	
	Strongly Agree	274 (30%)	177 (32%)	96 (28%)	
	Strongly Disagree	10 (1.1%)	2 (0.4%)	8 (2.3%)	
In India; RTs are not recognized enough for their contributions	Agree	235 (26%)	146 (26%)	89 (26%)	0.2
	Disagree	35 (3.9%)	21 (3.8%)	14 (4.0%)	
	Neutral	117 (13%)	65 (12%)	52 (15%)	
	Strongly Agree	511 (57%)	321 (58%)	189 (54%)	
	Strongly Disagree	6 (0.7%)	1 (0.2%)	5 (1.4%)	
Other careers are more attractive, so RTs change their profession.	Agree	177 (20%)	114 (21%)	62 (18%)	0.8
	Disagree	212 (23%)	132 (24%)	80 (23%)	
	Neutral	289 (32%)	175 (32%)	114 (33%)	
	Strongly Agree	145 (16%)	86 (16%)	59 (17%)	
	Strongly Disagree	81 (9.0%)	47 (8.5%)	34 (9.7%)	

Table: 4.2.4 Students response for satisfaction towards career prospects and learning resources

Satisfaction	Characteristic	N = 904
In my knowledge and experience, the standard of my institute matches with the international standards of respiratory therapy institutions	Agree	338 (37%)
	Strongly Agree	271 (30%)
	Neutral	190 (21%)
	Disagree	66 (7.3%)
	Strongly Disagree	39 (4.3%)
The physical facilities (e.g., classroom, furnishings, and computers) were appropriate	Agree	356 (39%)
	Strongly Agree	271 (30%)
	Neutral	184 (20%)
	Disagree	60 (6.6%)
	Strongly Disagree	33 (3.7%)
Situation of educational environment (school/college/institution) & clinical training site environment is safe and secure	Agree	392 (43%)
	Strongly Agree	334 (37%)
	Neutral	139 (15%)
	Disagree	29 (3.2%)
	Strongly Disagree	10 (1.1%)
There are adequate and quality education tools in our program	Agree	363 (40%)
	Strongly Agree	293 (32%)
	Neutral	155 (17%)
	Disagree	74 (8.2%)
	Strongly Disagree	19 (2.1%)
Various course are well coordinated to ensure equality among student	Agree	373 (41%)
	Strongly Agree	294 (33%)
	Neutral	174 (19%)
	Disagree	50 (5.5%)
	Strongly Disagree	13 (1.4%)
My faculty has excellent academic, practical and professional experiences	Strongly Agree	363 (40%)
	Agree	351 (39%)
	Neutral	132 (15%)
	Disagree	37 (4.1%)
	Strongly Disagree	21 (2.3%)
The faculty members are keen enough on the completion of the course curriculum	Agree	378 (42%)
	Strongly Agree	301 (33%)
	Neutral	164 (18%)
	Disagree	40 (4.4%)
	Strongly Disagree	21 (2.3%)
Benefits gained by the students from the clinical/practical training are excellent	Agree	351 (39%)
	Strongly Agree	330 (37%)
	Neutral	158 (17%)
	Disagree	42 (4.6%)
	Strongly Disagree	23 (2.5%)

My faculty has excellent academic, practical and professional experiences	Strongly Agree	358 (40%)
	Agree	353 (39%)
	Neutral	141 (16%)
	Disagree	35 (3.9%)
	Strongly Disagree	17 (1.9%)
The faculty members are keen enough on the completion of the course curriculum	Agree	362 (40%)
	Strongly Agree	309 (34%)
	Neutral	185 (20%)
	Disagree	33 (3.7%)
	Strongly Disagree	15 (1.7%)
There is good interaction between students and teaching faculty during the classes	Strongly Agree	346 (38%)
	Agree	343 (38%)
	Neutral	164 (18%)
	Disagree	31 (3.4%)
	Strongly Disagree	20 (2.2%)
The teachers covered all the key points of the current syllabus	Strongly Agree	322 (36%)
	Agree	320 (35%)
	Neutral	186 (21%)
	Disagree	39 (4.3%)
	Strongly Disagree	37 (4.1%)

Table: 4.2.5 Students response for satisfaction towards career prospects and learning resources based on the genders

Satisfaction	Characteristic	Overall, N = 904	Female, N = 554	Male, N = 349	p-value
In my knowledge and experience, the standard of my institute matches with the international standards of respiratory therapy institutions	Agree	338 (37%)	210 (38%)	127 (36%)	0.2
	Disagree	66 (7.3%)	44 (7.9%)	22 (6.3%)	
	Neutral	190 (21%)	127 (23%)	63 (18%)	
	Strongly Agree	271 (30%)	150 (27%)	121 (35%)	
	Strongly Disagree	39 (4.3%)	23 (4.2%)	16 (4.6%)	
The physical facilities (e.g., classroom, furnishings, and computers) were appropriate	Agree	356 (39%)	212 (38%)	143 (41%)	0.7
	Disagree	60 (6.6%)	41 (7.4%)	19 (5.4%)	
	Neutral	184 (20%)	117 (21%)	67 (19%)	
	Strongly Agree	271 (30%)	162 (29%)	109 (31%)	
	Strongly Disagree	33 (3.7%)	22 (4.0%)	11 (3.2%)	
Situation of educational environment (school/college/institution) & clinical training site environment is safe and secure	Agree	392 (43%)	243 (44%)	149 (43%)	0.5
	Disagree	29 (3.2%)	18 (3.2%)	11 (3.2%)	
	Neutral	139 (15%)	89 (16%)	49 (14%)	
	Strongly Agree	334 (37%)	197 (36%)	137 (39%)	
	Strongly Disagree	10 (1.1%)	7 (1.3%)	3 (0.9%)	
There are adequate and quality education tools in our program	Agree	363 (40%)	218 (39%)	145 (42%)	0.068
	Disagree	74 (8.2%)	55 (9.9%)	19 (5.4%)	
	Neutral	155 (17%)	99 (18%)	55 (16%)	
	Strongly Agree	293 (32%)	169 (31%)	124 (36%)	
	Strongly Disagree	19 (2.1%)	13 (2.3%)	6 (1.7%)	
Various course are well coordinated to ensure equality among student	Agree	373 (41%)	220 (40%)	152 (44%)	0.5
	Disagree	50 (5.5%)	42 (7.6%)	8 (2.3%)	
	Neutral	174 (19%)	109 (20%)	65 (19%)	
	Strongly Agree	294 (33%)	177 (32%)	117 (34%)	
	Strongly Disagree	13 (1.4%)	6 (1.1%)	7 (2.0%)	
My faculty has excellent academic, practical and professional experiences	Agree	351 (39%)	223 (40%)	128 (37%)	0.092
	Disagree	37 (4.1%)	24 (4.3%)	12 (3.4%)	
	Neutral	132 (15%)	86 (16%)	46 (13%)	
	Strongly Agree	363 (40%)	210 (38%)	153 (44%)	

	Strongly Disagree	21 (2.3%)	11 (2.0%)	10 (2.9%)	
The faculty members are keen enough on the completion of the course curriculum	Agree	378 (42%)	233 (42%)	144 (41%)	>0.9
	Disagree	40 (4.4%)	27 (4.9%)	13 (3.7%)	
	Neutral	164 (18%)	103 (19%)	61 (17%)	
	Strongly Agree	301 (33%)	179 (32%)	122 (35%)	
	Strongly Disagree	21 (2.3%)	12 (2.2%)	9 (2.6%)	
Benefits gained by the students from the clinical/practical training sites are excellent	Agree	351 (39%)	221 (40%)	130 (37%)	0.13
	Disagree	42 (4.6%)	29 (5.2%)	13 (3.7%)	
	Neutral	158 (17%)	104 (19%)	53 (15%)	
	Strongly Agree	330 (37%)	188 (34%)	142 (41%)	
	Strongly Disagree	23 (2.5%)	12 (2.2%)	11 (3.2%)	
My faculty has excellent academic, practical and professional experiences	Agree	353 (39%)	220 (40%)	132 (38%)	0.11
	Disagree	35 (3.9%)	23 (4.2%)	12 (3.4%)	
	Neutral	141 (16%)	98 (18%)	43 (12%)	
	Strongly Agree	358 (40%)	205 (37%)	153 (44%)	
	Strongly Disagree	17 (1.9%)	8 (1.4%)	9 (2.6%)	
The faculty members are keen enough on the completion of the course curriculum	Agree	362 (40%)	227 (41%)	134 (38%)	0.7
	Disagree	33 (3.7%)	19 (3.4%)	14 (4.0%)	
	Neutral	185 (20%)	119 (21%)	66 (19%)	
	Strongly Agree	309 (34%)	181 (33%)	128 (37%)	
	Strongly Disagree	15 (1.7%)	8 (1.4%)	7 (2.0%)	
There is good interaction between students and teaching faculty during the classes	Agree	343 (38%)	213 (38%)	129 (37%)	0.4
	Disagree	31 (3.4%)	20 (3.6%)	11 (3.2%)	
	Neutral	164 (18%)	110 (20%)	54 (15%)	
	Strongly Agree	346 (38%)	200 (36%)	146 (42%)	
	Strongly Disagree	20 (2.2%)	11 (2.0%)	9 (2.6%)	
The teachers covered all the key points of the current syllabus	Agree	320 (35%)	202 (36%)	118 (34%)	0.3
	Disagree	39 (4.3%)	23 (4.2%)	16 (4.6%)	
	Neutral	186 (21%)	123 (22%)	63 (18%)	
	Strongly Agree	322 (36%)	181 (33%)	140 (40%)	
	Strongly Disagree	37 (4.1%)	25 (4.5%)	12 (3.4%)	

Table: 4.2.6 Students response for suggestions towards career prospects and learning resources

Suggestions	Characteristic	N = 904
Career counselling help should be provided by the university	Strongly Agree	422 (47%)
	Agree	340 (38%)
	Neutral	124 (14%)
	Disagree	14 (1.5%)
	Strongly Disagree	4 (0.4%)
The clinical teaching is inadequate	Neutral	265 (29%)
	Disagree	261 (29%)
	Strongly Disagree	205 (23%)
	Agree	125 (14%)
	Strongly Agree	48 (5.3%)
There is no systematic training	Strongly Disagree	265 (29%)
	Agree	227 (25%)
	Strongly Agree	191 (21%)
	Disagree	172 (19%)
	Neutral	49 (5.4%)
There is an urgent need for establishing a regulatory body	Agree	436 (48%)
	Strongly Agree	343 (38%)
	Disagree	63 (7.0%)
	Neutral	35(4%)
	Strongly Disagree	27 (3.0%)

Table: 4.2.7 Students response for suggestions towards career prospects and learning resources based on the genders

Suggestion	Characteristic	Overall, N = 904	Female, N = 554	Male, N = 349	p-value
Career counselling help should be provided by the university	Agree	340 (38%)	202 (36%)	138 (40%)	0.6
	Disagree	14 (1.5%)	6 (1.1%)	8 (2.3%)	
	Neutral	124 (14%)	76 (14%)	48 (14%)	
	Strongly Agree	422 (47%)	267 (48%)	154 (44%)	
	Strongly Disagree	4 (0.4%)	3 (0.5%)	1 (0.3%)	
The clinical teaching is inadequate	Agree	125 (14%)	85 (15%)	40 (11%)	0.4
	Disagree	261 (29%)	152 (27%)	109 (31%)	
	Neutral	265 (29%)	173 (31%)	92 (26%)	
	Strongly Agree	48 (5.3%)	31 (5.6%)	17 (4.9%)	
	Strongly Disagree	205 (23%)	113 (20%)	91 (26%)	
There is no systematic training	Agree	227 (25%)	141 (25%)	85 (24%)	0.8
	Disagree	172 (19%)	105 (19%)	67 (19%)	
	Neutral	49 (5.4%)	29 (5.2%)	20 (5.7%)	
	Strongly Agree	191 (21%)	111 (20%)	80 (23%)	
	Strongly Disagree	265 (29%)	168 (30%)	97 (28%)	
There is no systematic training	Agree	255 (28%)	145 (26%)	109 (31%)	0.25
	Disagree	63 (7.0%)	36 (6.5%)	27 (7.7%)	
	Neutral	296 (33%)	204 (37%)	92 (26%)	
	Strongly Agree	263 (29%)	152 (27%)	111 (32%)	
	Strongly Disagree	27 (3.0%)	17 (3.1%)	10 (2.9%)	

Figure: 4.2.2 Radar plot for student survey

The “radar graph” is a promising tool that can be populated with existing data for use in feedback assessment for the students. Each axis of this circular radar graph represents one standard statement from our survey. Students reported lower score in suggestions compared to the score in other factors (Figure 4.2.2).

Table: 4.2.8 Factors associated with students' satisfaction

Variables	AOR	95% CI	P value
Type of Degree (Ref=Undergraduate)	1.78	1.03,2.98	0.05
Current Academic years (Ref=first year)	2.88	1.98,4.24	0.03
Do you have plan for moving abroad for Job (Ref= No)	1.28	1.02,2.21	0.04
Work is physically and emotionally challenging (Ref= Not agreed)	2.35	1.25,4.56	0.01
In India; RTs are not recognized enough for their contributions (Ref= Agreed)	2.98	1.20,3.89	0.02

AOR-Adjusted odds ratio; CI-Confident interval

The students studying post-graduation in RT were 1.78 times more unsatisfied compared with undergraduates. Compared with first year students, others were 2.88 times more likely unsatisfied about the learning resources. The students who want to move abroad were 1.28 times more unsatisfied about the learning resources and career prospects. The students who perceived that In India; RTs are not recognized enough for their contributions were 2.98 times more likely to be not satisfied (AOR=2.98, CI=1.20,3.89). Students who perceived RT works are physically and mentally challenging were 2.35 times more unsatisfied about the carrier prospects and learning resources (Table: 4.2.8).

4.3 Development and Validation of Questionnaire for assessing Perceptions, job satisfaction and its impact on career progression among Respiratory Therapists in India.

Three hundred and eighty-eight Respiratory Therapists (RT) were included in the analysis after the exclusion of twelve responses as an invalid case or not willing to participate in the survey. Majority of the respondents (n=106, 27%) were from Karnataka and 88% (n=342) of them are 21-30 years old and over half of the respondents were female (61%) (Table 4.4.1, Figure 4.4.1). Both EFA and CFA were then performed to assess the validity of the tool.

Table: 4.3.1 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics							
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis
P1	388	3	5	4.68	0.473	-0.837	-1.104
P2	388	1	5	4.31	0.875	-1.429	2.194
P3	388	2	5	4.88	0.374	-3.443	14.284
P4	388	2	5	4.76	0.515	-2.542	8.006
P5	388	1	5	4.52	0.649	-1.409	2.779
P6	388	1	5	3.55	1.12	-0.529	-0.391
P7	388	1	5	4.04	0.914	-0.918	0.831
P8	388	1	5	2.8	1.21	0.154	-0.744
P10	388	1	5	3.79	1.118	-0.713	-0.361
P11	388	1	5	3.9	0.987	-0.672	0.012
P12	388	1	5	3.54	1.04	-0.499	-0.341
P13	388	1	5	2.99	1.107	-0.07	-0.873
P14	388	1	5	3.52	1.025	-0.382	-0.535
P15	388	1	5	4.34	0.836	-1.448	2.452
P16	388	1	5	4.22	0.861	-1.103	1.067
P17	388	1	5	3.3	1.096	-0.147	-0.595
P18	388	1	5	3.79	1.125	-0.792	-0.112
P19	388	1	5	4.53	0.87	-2.181	4.71
P20	388	1	5	4.01	0.919	-0.788	0.341
P21	388	1	5	2.96	1.099	0.152	-0.655
P22	388	1	5	3.35	1.015	-0.2	-0.579
P23	388	1	5	3.26	1.203	-0.206	-0.899
P24	388	1	5	3.3	1.07	-0.085	-0.582

P25	388	1	5	3.45	1.024	-0.281	-0.392
P26	388	1	5	3.48	1	-0.287	-0.329
A1	388	2	5	4.65	0.611	-1.805	3.264
A2	388	1	5	1.9	0.877	1.033	1.059
A3	388	1	5	2.55	1.083	0.462	-0.32
A4	388	1	5	4.23	0.864	-1.239	1.704
A5	388	1	5	4.05	0.975	-1.09	0.934
A6	388	1	5	3.96	0.985	-0.824	0.203
S1	388	1	5	2.27	1.195	0.497	-0.652
S2	388	1	5	3.08	1.247	-0.093	-1.012
S3	388	1	5	3.64	0.98	-0.568	0.008
S4	388	1	5	3.69	1.018	-0.718	0.065
S5	388	1	5	2.65	1.157	0.396	-0.675
S6	388	1	5	3.02	1.126	0.052	-0.878
S7	388	1	5	4.23	0.815	-1.198	2.075
S8	388	1	5	2.88	1.077	0.205	-0.509
S9	388	1	5	3.81	0.955	-0.724	0.342
S10	388	1	5	2.97	1.066	-0.026	-0.623
S11	388	1	5	3.31	1.22	-0.388	-0.749
S12	388	1	3	1.55	0.872	1.006	-0.924
S13	388	0	5	4	1.289	-1.458	1.808
S14	388	0	5	2.64	1.556	-0.361	-0.854
S15	388	0	5	3.07	1.598	-0.707	-0.527
S16	388	0	5	3	1.563	-0.685	-0.542
S17	388	0	5	2.8	1.511	-0.55	-0.543
S18	388	0	5	2.68	1.469	-0.483	-0.627

Figure: 4.3.1 Scree plot for Faculty SQ with three items

Table 4.3.2: Factor Loadings and Communalities

Factor	Items	Questionnaires	Estimation	communalities
Perception	.P1	RT is a humanitarian, caring profession, where ethical standards of care are maintained	0.211	0.228
	.P6	RT receives recognition from the community	0.64	0.446
	.P7	RT are decision makers in Respiratory patient care	0.471	0.368
	.P8	RT as a profession does not require eligibility criteria (For joining the course)	1.351	0.263
	.P10	RT profession is equal to other healthcare disciplines	1.134	0.119
	.P11	I think Respiratory Therapy would be a great profession for my children	0.615	0.436
	.P12	Demanding work schedule	1.048	0.177
	.P13	Not enough new graduates to fill increasing number of jobs]	1.184	0.198
	.P14	Work is physically and emotionally challenging	1.019	0.225
	.P15	In India, RTs are not recognized enough for their contributions	0.653	0.442
	.P18	Lack of knowledge about this profession	1.224	0.245
	.P20	Increased stress on Respiratory Therapists	0.843	0.328
	.P21	Higher pay for Respiratory Therapists	1.031	0.189
	.P22	More job choices for presently working Respiratory Therapists	0.825	0.249
	.P23	Lower quality care for patients	1.438	0.198
	.P24	Respiratory Therapists will be leaving for other jobs	1.069	0.323
	.P25	More respect for Respiratory Therapists	0.76	0.369
.P26	Improvement in workplace environment	0.849	0.255	
	.S1	I am Frustrated	1.419	0.417

Satisfaction	.S2	Happy (I am happy with my career choice)	0.997	0.507
	.S3	Satisfied (My career as an RT is rewarding)	0.905	0.655
	.S4	I would recommend RT as a career choice to me immediate family of close friend	0.668	0.541
	.S5	I feel Respiratory Therapy is similar to the servants job	1.161	0.324
	.S6	I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do	1.178	0.289
	.S8	There is really too little chance for promotion on my job	1.109	0.186
	.S9	When I do a good job, I receive the recognition/appreciation for it that I should receive	0.73	0.321
	.S10	I sometimes feel my job is meaningless	1.109	0.389
	.S11	I do not feel that the work I do is appreciated	0.7	0.248
	.S15	There is too much bickering and fighting at work	1.699	0.27
	.S16	There are tremendous opportunities for personal growth	1.774	0.277
	.S17	Work assignments are not fully explained	1.843	0.218
	.S18	I am satisfied with the career ladder and financial benefits of a Respiratory Therapist	1.953	0.118
	Attitude	.A3	Low salary and allowances	0.888
.A4		Rewards and incentives	0.354	0.53
.A5		Public perceptions of the RT profession	0.212	0.554
.A6		Relationship with other disciplines	0.374	0.566
KMO and Bartlett's Test				
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy			0.836	
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square		5676.37	
	Df		666	
	Sig.		0.0001	

4.3.1 Exploratory Factor Analysis

EFA was conducted on the Likert scale items for each factor of the questionnaires. According to the predefined models, the perception factor contained 26 items (P1–P26), the satisfaction factor contained 18 items (S1–S18), and attitude factor contained 6 items (A1-A6). Normality assessment usually rejects if the ratio of skewness is $> \pm 1$ and/or kurtosis is $> \pm 2$ [75]. The items' distribution deviated from the normality on above mentioned range removed from the model (Table: 4.3.1).

The Kaiser-Meyer-Oklin (KMO) is a measure that provides an approach to comparing the zero-order correlations to the partial correlations between pairs of variables [76]. The KMO in the study model was 0.90; Kaiser (1974) stated that if the KMO is > 0.50 , it is acceptable. The closer the KMO is to 1, the better the correlations between the pairs of variables that can be explained by the other variables [77] (Table 4.3.2).

The results of the EFAs for perception showed that 8 items did not load (factor loading less than 0.30) on the factor well; P2 to P5, P9, P16,P17,and P19. For the attitude factor, A1 and A2 item and satisfaction factor, S7, S12, S13, and S14 were not loaded well. Therefore, they were sequentially trimmed from the model. The modified model on perception comprised of P1, P6-P8, P10-15, P18, and P20-26, satisfaction comprised S1-S7, S8-S11 and S15-S18, attitude factor contains A3-A6 and accounted for 61.2% of the total variance (Figure:4.3.1).

Table: 4.3.3 Correlation matrixes between the factors

	Perception	Satisfaction	Attitude
Perception	1	-	-
Satisfaction	-0.713	1	-
Attitude	-0.715	0.79	1

Table 4.3.4: Confirmatory Factor Analysis Process for scale

χ^2	RMSEA	TLI	CFI	GFI	χ^2 / df	P value
2625	0.05	0.90	0.98	0.94	4.4	0.02

Pearson's correlation coefficients were calculated to explore the inter-relationships between factors (Table: 4.3.3). The measurement model fit using CFA is shown in Figure 2. The model fit the data adequately with a good GFI (0.94), TLI (0.90) and RMSEA (0.05). The raw χ^2 is 2625 and χ^2 / df is 4.49 with p-value < 0.01 (Table: 4.3.4).

Table 4.3.5: Validity and Reliability Measures

	AVE	CR	MSV
Perception	0.84	0.73	0.29
Satisfaction	0.81	0.70	0.21
Attitude	0.91	0.78	0.22

The AVE of the constructs in the study were measured and compared to the inter-factor correlations [78]. Preliminary evidence of convergent validity was determined when the AVE of each construct was higher than its correlation with other constructs. While discriminant validity of the competency scale was preliminarily determined by assessing the Maximum Shared Variance (MSV), and found to be lower than the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for all of the constructs in the scale [79]. Convergent and Discriminant validities results are available in (Table 4.3.5).

Figure: 4.3.2 SEM results of the confirmatory factor analysis for the three-factor model

4.4. Perceptions, job satisfaction and its impact on career progression among Respiratory Therapists in India

Table: 4.4.1 Demographical detail of the participants

Characteristic	N = 388
State	
Karnataka	106 (27%)
I work abroad	82 (21%)
Kerala	72 (19%)
Tamil Nadu	64 (16%)
Telangana	34 (8.8%)
Maharashtra	21 (5.4%)
Rajasthan	3 (0.8%)
Tripura	2 (0.5%)
Odisha	1 (0.3%)
Punjab	1 (0.3%)
West Bengal	1 (0.3%)
Andhra Pradesh	1 (0.3%)
Age	
21-30	342 (88%)
31-40	37 (9.5%)
41-50	7 (1.8%)
Above 50	1 (0.3%)
Less than 20	1 (0.3%)
Gender	
Female	238 (61%)
Male	150 (39%)
Married	
No	264 (68%)
Yes	117 (30%)
Not prefer to say	7 (1.8%)
Degree	
Bachelor in RT	308 (79%)
Master in RT	53 (14%)
Diploma/Advanced Diploma in RT	22 (5.7%)
On job training	3 (0.8%)
PhD/Doctoral	2 (0.5%)
Employment Status	
Full time	361 (93%)
Not working	20 (5.2%)
Part time	7 (1.8%)
Role	
Critical care (ICU and ER)	293 (76%)
Education/Academic Institution (Ass. Professor, Lecturer, Tutor, Demonstrator etc.)	32 (8.2%)

Not working	10 (2.6%)
Outpatient (such as diagnostics and pulmonary rehabilitation)	21 (5.4%)
Private Clinic (rehabilitation centre, home care centre, sleep clinic)	8 (2.1%)
Non-critical care (ward and long-term)	6 (1.5%)
Work in a medical equipment company	4 (1.0%)
Administration	2 (0.5%)
Respiratory therapist	2 (0.5%)
Bronchoscopy	1 (0.3%)
Entrepreneur	1 (0.3%)
Hospital setup including (spirometry and advanced spirometry, bronchoscopy, thoracoscopy pulmonary rehabilitation, ICU setup and ward setup)	1 (0.3%)
Outpatient, non-critical care and critical care.	1 (0.3%)
PG student	1 (0.3%)
Pulmonary Rehabilitation freelance	1 (0.3%)
Pulmonology & critical care	1 (0.3%)
Student	1 (0.3%)
Tutor and Respiratory Therapist	1 (0.3%)
Experience	
1-5 years	226 (58%)
< one year	93 (24%)
6-10 years	45 (12%)
11-20 years	19 (4.9%)
> 20 years	5 (1.3%)
Working hours	
8 hours	224 (58%)
12 hours	90 (23%)
< 8 hours	62 (16%)
> 12 hours	12 (3.1%)
Primary shift	
Alternative	194 (50%)
Day	183 (47%)
24 Hours	8 (2.1%)
Night	3 (0.8%)
Monthly income	
20,001-30,000	174 (45%)
Above 100,000	70 (18%)
10,000-20,000	64 (16%)
30,001-40,000	27 (7.0%)
40,001-60,000	19 (4.9%)
below 10000	21 (5.4%)
60,001-100,000	13 (3.4%)

Of the 388 RT respondents, 27% (n=106) were from the state of Karnataka, 19% (n=72) from the state of Kerala and 16% (n=64) responded from the state of Tamilnadu. Among them, 238 were female (61%) and 150 were male (39%) (Figure: 4.4.1). The age range included ranged from 21 yrs to above 50 years. Around 342 (88%) respondents were between 21-30 yrs old, 37 (9.5%) were between 31-40 years, and 7 (1.8 %) was between 41-50 years (Table: 4.4.1).

The RT respondents were having a bachelor degree was 79%, Diploma 22/388 (5.7%) and Master degree 53/388 (14%). Majority of them were working full time (361/388, 93%), and very few of them were working as a part time faculty (n=7, [1.8%]). Most of the respondents (n=293, [76%]) were working in the critical care unit along with the ICU or ER team. Table 4.4.1 provides further details on the demographic characteristics of the participants.

Figure: 4.4.1 Responded Respiratory Therapist mapping

Table: 4.4.2 Perception of Respiratory Therapists

Characteristic	N = 388
RT is a humanitarian, caring profession, where ethical standards of care are maintained	
Strongly agree	264 (68%)
Agree	123 (32%)
Neutral	1 (0.3%)
Disagree	0 (0)
Strongly Disagree	0 (0)
RT receives recognition from the community	
Agree	136 (35%)
Neutral	101 (26%)
Strongly agree	84 (22%)
Disagree	45 (12%)
Strongly Disagree	22 (5.7%)
RT are decision makers in Respiratory patient care	
Agree	159 (41%)
Strongly agree	136 (35%)
Neutral	73 (19%)
Disagree	13 (3.4%)
Strongly Disagree	7 (1.8%)
RT as a profession does not require eligibility criteria (For joining the course)	
Neutral	139 (36%)
Disagree	81 (21%)
Strongly Disagree	69 (18%)
Agree	57 (15%)
Strongly agree	42 (11%)
RT profession is equal to other healthcare disciplines	
Agree	139 (36%)
Strongly agree	122 (31%)
Neutral	65 (17%)
Disagree	49 (13%)
Strongly Disagree	13 (3.4%)
I think Respiratory Therapy would be a great profession for my children	
Agree	137 (35%)
Strongly agree	125 (32%)
Neutral	96 (25%)
Disagree	22 (5.7%)
Strongly Disagree	8 (2.1%)
Demanding work schedule]	
Agree	158 (41%)

Neutral	97 (25%)
Strongly agree	66 (17%)
Disagree	53 (14%)
Strongly Disagree	14 (3.6%)
Not enough new graduates to fill increasing number of jobs	
Agree	117 (30%)
Disagree	105 (27%)
Neutral	103 (27%)
Strongly Disagree	35 (9.0%)
Strongly agree	28 (7.2%)
Work is physically and emotionally challenging	
Agree	153 (39%)
Neutral	100 (26%)
Strongly agree	64 (16%)
Disagree	61 (16%)
Strongly Disagree	10 (2.6%)
In India, RTs are not recognized enough for their contributions	
Strongly agree	200 (52%)
Agree	137 (35%)
Neutral	38 (9.8%)
Disagree	8 (2.1%)
Strongly Disagree	5 (1.3%)
Lack of knowledge about this profession	
Agree	140 (36%)
Strongly agree	121 (31%)
Neutral	71 (18%)
Disagree	38 (9.8%)
Strongly Disagree	18 (4.6%)
Increased stress on Respiratory Therapists	
Agree	155 (40%)
Strongly agree	133 (34%)
Neutral	77 (20%)
Disagree	18 (4.6%)
Strongly Disagree	5 (1.3%)
Higher pay for Respiratory Therapists	
Neutral	130 (34%)
Disagree	108 (28%)
Agree	80 (21%)
Strongly agree	38 (9.8%)
Strongly Disagree	32 (8.2%)
There are more job choices for presently working RTs	
Agree	133 (34%)

Neutral	124 (32%)
Disagree	70 (18%)
Strongly agree	49 (13%)
Strongly Disagree	12 (3.1%)
Lower quality care for patients	
Agree	111 (29%)
Neutral	100 (26%)
Disagree	78 (20%)
Strongly agree	66 (17%)
Strongly Disagree	33 (8.5%)
Respiratory Therapists will be leaving for other jobs	
Neutral	144 (37%)
Agree	99 (26%)
Disagree	67 (17%)
Strongly agree	60 (15%)
Strongly Disagree	18 (4.6%)
More respect for Respiratory Therapists	
Neutral	133 (34%)
Agree	128 (33%)
Strongly agree	62 (16%)
Disagree	51 (13%)
Strongly Disagree	14 (3.6%)
Improvement in workplace environment	
Neutral	135 (35%)
Agree	132 (34%)
Strongly agree	62 (16%)
Disagree	47 (12%)
Strongly Disagree	15 (3.9%)
Strongly Disagree	12 (3.1%)

In total, 98.7% of respondents either agree or strongly agree that RT is a humanitarian, caring profession, where ethical standards of care are maintained. Around 57% of them respondents either agree or strongly agree that RT received recognition from the community. 76% of RT respondents either agree or strongly agree that RT is the decision makers in the respiratory patient care. In average, more than 30% of the faculties (P=0.02) either agree or strongly agree that RT as a profession does not require eligibility criteria for the students to join the course. 37.2% of the faculties either agree or strongly agree that not enough new graduates to fill increasing

number of jobs in the current situation. Majority (87%) of the faculties felt that RTs are not recognized enough for their contributions in India. In addition, they reflected (74%) that stress on the RT also increased. About the patient care, few of them (46%) stated that low quality of care (Table: 4.4.3).

Table: 4.4.3 Respiratory Therapists Perceptions based on the gender

Characteristic	Overall, N = 388	Female, N = 238	Male, N = 150	p-value
RT is a humanitarian, caring profession, where ethical standards of care are maintained				0.071
Agree	123 (32%)	84 (35%)	39 (26%)	
Neutral	1 (0.3%)	1 (0.4%)	0 (0%)	
Strongly agree	264 (68%)	153 (64%)	111 (74%)	
RT receives recognition from the community				0.001
Agree	136 (35%)	81 (34%)	55 (37%)	
Disagree	45 (12%)	38 (16%)	7 (4.7%)	
Neutral	101 (26%)	54 (23%)	47 (31%)	
Strongly agree	84 (22%)	47 (20%)	37 (25%)	
Strongly Disagree	22 (5.7%)	18 (7.6%)	4 (2.7%)	
RT are decision makers in Respiratory patient care				0.8
Agree	159 (41%)	99 (42%)	60 (40%)	
Disagree	13 (3.4%)	7 (2.9%)	6 (4.0%)	
Neutral	73 (19%)	48 (20%)	25 (17%)	
Strongly agree	136 (35%)	79 (33%)	57 (38%)	
Strongly Disagree	7 (1.8%)	5 (2.1%)	2 (1.3%)	
RT as a profession does not require eligibility criteria (For joining the course)				0.024
Agree	57 (15%)	28 (12%)	29 (19%)	
Disagree	81 (21%)	48 (20%)	33 (22%)	
Neutral	139 (36%)	95 (40%)	44 (29%)	
Strongly agree	42 (11%)	20 (8.4%)	22 (15%)	
Strongly Disagree	69 (18%)	47 (20%)	22 (15%)	
RT profession is equal to other healthcare disciplines				0.5
Agree	139 (36%)	87 (37%)	52 (35%)	
Disagree	49 (13%)	32 (13%)	17 (11%)	
Neutral	65 (17%)	41 (17%)	24 (16%)	

Strongly agree	122 (31%)	68 (29%)	54 (36%)	
Strongly Disagree	13 (3.4%)	10 (4.2%)	3 (2.0%)	
I think Respiratory Therapy would be a great profession for my children				
Agree	137 (35%)	76 (32%)	61 (41%)	0.2
Disagree	22 (5.7%)	15 (6.3%)	7 (4.7%)	
Neutral	96 (25%)	59 (25%)	37 (25%)	
Strongly agree	125 (32%)	85 (36%)	40 (27%)	
Strongly Disagree	8 (2.1%)	3 (1.3%)	5 (3.3%)	
Demanding work schedule				
Agree	158 (41%)	96 (40%)	62 (41%)	0.5
Disagree	53 (14%)	34 (14%)	19 (13%)	
Neutral	97 (25%)	65 (27%)	32 (21%)	
Strongly agree	66 (17%)	35 (15%)	31 (21%)	
Strongly Disagree	14 (3.6%)	8 (3.4%)	6 (4.0%)	
Not enough new graduates to fill increasing number of jobs				
Agree	117 (30%)	73 (31%)	44 (29%)	0.003
Disagree	105 (27%)	70 (29%)	35 (23%)	
Neutral	103 (27%)	68 (29%)	35 (23%)	
Strongly agree	28 (7.2%)	8 (3.4%)	20 (13%)	
Strongly Disagree	35 (9.0%)	19 (8.0%)	16 (11%)	
Work is physically and emotionally challenging				
Agree	153 (39%)	93 (39%)	60 (40%)	0.6
Disagree	61 (16%)	40 (17%)	21 (14%)	
Neutral	100 (26%)	65 (27%)	35 (23%)	
Strongly agree	64 (16%)	35 (15%)	29 (19%)	
Strongly Disagree	10 (2.6%)	5 (2.1%)	5 (3.3%)	
In India, RTs are not recognized enough for their contributions				
Agree	137 (35%)	87 (37%)	50 (33%)	0.3
Disagree	8 (2.1%)	5 (2.1%)	3 (2.0%)	
Neutral	38 (9.8%)	17 (7.1%)	21 (14%)	
Strongly agree	200 (52%)	126 (53%)	74 (49%)	
Strongly Disagree	5 (1.3%)	3 (1.3%)	2 (1.3%)	
Lack of knowledge about this profession				
Agree	140 (36%)	85 (36%)	55 (37%)	0.7
Disagree	38 (9.8%)	23 (9.7%)	15 (10%)	
Neutral	71 (18%)	40 (17%)	31 (21%)	
Strongly agree	121 (31%)	80 (34%)	41 (27%)	
Strongly Disagree	18 (4.6%)	10 (4.2%)	8 (5.3%)	
Increased stress on Respiratory Therapists				
Agree	155 (40%)	100 (42%)	55 (37%)	

Disagree	18 (4.6%)	9 (3.8%)	9 (6.0%)	0.2
Neutral	77 (20%)	44 (18%)	33 (22%)	
Strongly agree	133 (34%)	84 (35%)	49 (33%)	
Strongly Disagree	5 (1.3%)	1 (0.4%)	4 (2.7%)	
Higher pay for Respiratory Therapists				0.4
Agree	80 (21%)	48 (20%)	32 (21%)	
Disagree	108 (28%)	64 (27%)	44 (29%)	
Neutral	130 (34%)	88 (37%)	42 (28%)	
Strongly agree	38 (9.8%)	21 (8.8%)	17 (11%)	
Strongly Disagree	32 (8.2%)	17 (7.1%)	15 (10%)	0.2
More job choices for presently working Respiratory Therapists				
Agree	133 (34%)	83 (35%)	50 (33%)	
Disagree	70 (18%)	43 (18%)	27 (18%)	
Neutral	124 (32%)	82 (34%)	42 (28%)	
Strongly agree	49 (13%)	25 (11%)	24 (16%)	
Strongly Disagree	12 (3.1%)	5 (2.1%)	7 (4.7%)	0.007
Lower quality care for patients				
Agree	111 (29%)	58 (24%)	53 (35%)	
Disagree	78 (20%)	56 (24%)	22 (15%)	
Neutral	100 (26%)	71 (30%)	29 (19%)	
Strongly agree	66 (17%)	35 (15%)	31 (21%)	0.3
Strongly Disagree	33 (8.5%)	18 (7.6%)	15 (10%)	
Respiratory Therapists will be leaving for other jobs				
Agree	99 (26%)	59 (25%)	40 (27%)	
Disagree	67 (17%)	49 (21%)	18 (12%)	
Neutral	144 (37%)	87 (37%)	57 (38%)	
Strongly agree	60 (15%)	33 (14%)	27 (18%)	0.7
Strongly Disagree	18 (4.6%)	10 (4.2%)	8 (5.3%)	
More respect for Respiratory Therapists				
Agree	128 (33%)	81 (34%)	47 (31%)	
Disagree	51 (13%)	34 (14%)	17 (11%)	
Neutral	133 (34%)	81 (34%)	52 (35%)	0.2
Strongly agree	62 (16%)	35 (15%)	27 (18%)	
Strongly Disagree	14 (3.6%)	7 (2.9%)	7 (4.7%)	
Improvement in workplace environment				
Agree	132 (34%)	78 (33%)	54 (36%)	
Disagree	47 (12%)	32 (13%)	15 (10%)	
Neutral	135 (35%)	90 (38%)	45 (30%)	
Strongly agree	62 (16%)	33 (14%)	29 (19%)	
Strongly Disagree	12 (3.1%)	5 (2.1%)	7 (4.7%)	

Table: 4.4.4 Satisfaction of Respiratory Therapists

Characteristic	N = 388
I feel Respiratory Therapy is similar to the servants job	
Strongly Disagree	146 (38%)
Neutral	130 (34%)
Disagree	62 (16%)
Agree	29 (7.5%)
Strongly agree	21 (5.4%)
I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do	
Agree	102 (26%)
Neutral	96 (25%)
Disagree	86 (22%)
Strongly agree	56 (14%)
Strongly Disagree	48 (12%)
There is really too little chance for promotion on my job	
Agree	165 (43%)
Neutral	104 (27%)
Strongly agree	71 (18%)
Disagree	37 (9.5%)
Strongly Disagree	11 (2.8%)
When I do a good job, I receive the recognition/appreciation for it that I should receive	
Agree	176 (45%)
Neutral	79 (20%)
Strongly agree	79 (20%)
Disagree	41 (11%)
Strongly Disagree	13 (3.4%)
I sometimes feel my job is meaningless	
Disagree	137 (35%)
Neutral	96 (25%)
Agree	64 (16%)
Strongly Disagree	61 (16%)
Strongly agree	30 (7.7%)
I do not feel that the work I do is appreciated	
Disagree	112 (29%)
Neutral	104 (27%)
Agree	103 (27%)
Strongly agree	39 (10%)
Strongly Disagree	30 (7.7%)
There is too much bickering and fighting at work	
Neutral	140 (36%)
Disagree	110 (28%)

Agree	69 (18%)
Strongly Disagree	36 (9.3%)
Strongly agree	33 (8.5%)
There are tremendous opportunities for personal growth	
Agree	171 (44%)
Strongly agree	94 (24%)
Neutral	88 (23%)
Disagree	26 (6.7%)
Strongly Disagree	9 (2.3%)
Work assignments are not fully explained	
Neutral	134 (35%)
Agree	97 (25%)
Disagree	95 (24%)
Strongly Disagree	34 (8.8%)
Strongly agree	28 (7.2%)
I am satisfied with the career ladder and financial benefits of a Respiratory Therapist	
Agree	123 (32%)
Neutral	101 (26%)
Strongly agree	68 (18%)
Disagree	55 (14%)
Strongly Disagree	41 (11%)
Work environment	
Neutral	96 (25%)
Agree	89 (23%)
Disagree	78 (20%)
Not applicable	64 (16%)
Strongly agree	41 (11%)
Strongly Disagree	20 (5.2%)
Low salary and allowances	
Agree	113 (29%)
Neutral	88 (23%)
Strongly agree	74 (19%)
Not applicable	54 (14%)
Disagree	47 (12%)
Strongly Disagree	12 (3.1%)
Rewards and incentives	
Agree	122 (31%)
Neutral	88 (23%)
Strongly agree	59 (15%)
Not applicable	52 (13%)
Disagree	51 (13%)
Strongly Disagree	15 (3.9%)

Public perceptions of the RT profession	
Neutral	120 (31%)
Agree	92 (24%)
Disagree	61 (16%)
Not applicable	57 (15%)
Strongly agree	45 (12%)
Strongly Disagree	13 (3.4%)
Relationship with other disciplines	
Neutral	117 (30%)
Agree	93 (24%)
Disagree	70 (18%)
Not applicable	56 (14%)
Strongly agree	31 (8.0%)
Strongly Disagree	21 (5.4%)

Table: 4.4.5 Satisfaction of faculties based on genders

Characteristic	Overall, N = 388	Female, N = 238	Male, N = 150	p-value
I would recommend RT as a career choice to me immediate family of close friend				0.3
Agree	149 (38%)	96 (40%)	53 (35%)	
Disagree	27 (7.0%)	13 (5.5%)	14 (9.3%)	
Neutral	72 (19%)	41 (17%)	31 (21%)	
Strongly agree	133 (34%)	85 (36%)	48 (32%)	
Strongly Disagree	7 (1.8%)	3 (1.3%)	4 (2.7%)	
I feel Respiratory Therapy is similar to the servants job				0.039
Agree	29 (7.5%)	16 (6.7%)	13 (8.7%)	
Disagree	62 (16%)	38 (16%)	24 (16%)	
Neutral	130 (34%)	78 (33%)	52 (35%)	
Strongly agree	21 (5.4%)	7 (2.9%)	14 (9.3%)	
Strongly Disagree	146 (38%)	99 (42%)	47 (31%)	
I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do				0.053
Agree	102 (26%)	69 (29%)	33 (22%)	
Disagree	86 (22%)	57 (24%)	29 (19%)	
Neutral	96 (25%)	57 (24%)	39 (26%)	
Strongly agree	56 (14%)	25 (11%)	31 (21%)	
Strongly Disagree	48 (12%)	30 (13%)	18 (12%)	
There is really too little chance for promotion on my job				0.8
Agree	165 (43%)	103 (43%)	62 (41%)	

Disagree	37 (9.5%)	24 (10%)	13 (8.7%)	
Neutral	104 (27%)	65 (27%)	39 (26%)	
Strongly agree	71 (18%)	41 (17%)	30 (20%)	
Strongly Disagree	11 (2.8%)	5 (2.1%)	6 (4.0%)	
When I do a good job, I receive the recognition/appreciation for it that I should receive				0.6
Agree	176 (45%)	103 (43%)	73 (49%)	
Disagree	41 (11%)	28 (12%)	13 (8.7%)	
Neutral	79 (20%)	52 (22%)	27 (18%)	
Strongly agree	79 (20%)	46 (19%)	33 (22%)	
Strongly Disagree	13 (3.4%)	9 (3.8%)	4 (2.7%)	
I sometimes feel my job is meaningless				0.12
Agree	64 (16%)	35 (15%)	29 (19%)	
Disagree	137 (35%)	91 (38%)	46 (31%)	
Neutral	96 (25%)	64 (27%)	32 (21%)	
Strongly agree	30 (7.7%)	14 (5.9%)	16 (11%)	
Strongly Disagree	61 (16%)	34 (14%)	27 (18%)	
I do not feel that the work I do is appreciated				0.044
Agree	103 (27%)	54 (23%)	49 (33%)	
Disagree	112 (29%)	73 (31%)	39 (26%)	
Neutral	104 (27%)	71 (30%)	33 (22%)	
Strongly agree	39 (10%)	19 (8.0%)	20 (13%)	
Strongly Disagree	30 (7.7%)	21 (8.8%)	9 (6.0%)	
There is too much bickering and fighting at work				0.2
Agree	69 (18%)	44 (18%)	25 (17%)	
Disagree	110 (28%)	73 (31%)	37 (25%)	
Neutral	140 (36%)	82 (34%)	58 (39%)	
Strongly agree	33 (8.5%)	15 (6.3%)	18 (12%)	
Strongly Disagree	36 (9.3%)	24 (10%)	12 (8.0%)	
There are tremendous opportunities for personal growth				>0.9
Agree	171 (44%)	107 (45%)	64 (43%)	
Disagree	26 (6.7%)	16 (6.7%)	10 (6.7%)	
Neutral	88 (23%)	52 (22%)	36 (24%)	
Strongly agree	94 (24%)	57 (24%)	37 (25%)	
Strongly Disagree	9 (2.3%)	6 (2.5%)	3 (2.0%)	
Work assignments are not fully explained				0.011
Agree	97 (25%)	56 (24%)	41 (27%)	
Disagree	95 (24%)	63 (26%)	32 (21%)	
Neutral	134 (35%)	89 (37%)	45 (30%)	
Strongly agree	28 (7.2%)	9 (3.8%)	19 (13%)	

Strongly Disagree	34 (8.8%)	21 (8.8%)	13 (8.7%)	
I am satisfied with the career ladder and financial benefits of a Respiratory Therapist				0.1
Agree	123 (32%)	86 (36%)	37 (25%)	
Disagree	55 (14%)	36 (15%)	19 (13%)	
Neutral	101 (26%)	56 (24%)	45 (30%)	
Strongly agree	68 (18%)	36 (15%)	32 (21%)	
Strongly Disagree	41 (11%)	24 (10%)	17 (11%)	
Work environment				0.3
Not applicable	64 (16%)	39 (16%)	25 (17%)	
Agree	89 (23%)	61 (26%)	28 (19%)	
Disagree	78 (20%)	48 (20%)	30 (20%)	
Neutral	96 (25%)	56 (24%)	40 (27%)	
Strongly agree	41 (11%)	20 (8.4%)	21 (14%)	
Strongly Disagree	20 (5.2%)	14 (5.9%)	6 (4.0%)	
Low salary and allowances				0.3
Not applicable	54 (14%)	32 (13%)	22 (15%)	
Agree	113 (29%)	76 (32%)	37 (25%)	
Disagree	47 (12%)	28 (12%)	19 (13%)	
Neutral	88 (23%)	57 (24%)	31 (21%)	
Strongly agree	74 (19%)	37 (16%)	37 (25%)	
Strongly Disagree	12 (3.1%)	8 (3.4%)	4 (2.7%)	
Rewards and incentives				0.4
Not applicable	52 (13%)	34 (14%)	18 (12%)	
Agree	122 (31%)	77 (32%)	45 (30%)	
Disagree	51 (13%)	31 (13%)	20 (13%)	
Neutral	88 (23%)	58 (24%)	30 (20%)	
Strongly agree	59 (15%)	29 (12%)	30 (20%)	
Strongly Disagree	15 (3.9%)	9 (3.8%)	6 (4.0%)	
Public perceptions of the RT profession				0.4
Not applicable	57 (15%)	34 (14%)	23 (15%)	
Agree	92 (24%)	60 (25%)	32 (21%)	
Disagree	61 (16%)	37 (16%)	24 (16%)	
Neutral	120 (31%)	78 (33%)	42 (28%)	
Strongly agree	45 (12%)	21 (8.8%)	24 (16%)	
Strongly Disagree	13 (3.4%)	8 (3.4%)	5 (3.3%)	
Relationship with other disciplines				0.2
Not applicable	56 (14%)	36 (15%)	20 (13%)	
Agree	93 (24%)	54 (23%)	39 (26%)	
Disagree	70 (18%)	44 (18%)	26 (17%)	
Neutral	117 (30%)	73 (31%)	44 (29%)	
Strongly agree	31 (8.0%)	14 (5.9%)	17 (11%)	
Strongly Disagree	21 (5.4%)	17 (7.1%)	4 (2.7%)	

In average, 54% of the RTs either disagree or strongly disagree that RT is similar to servant job. At the same time, 40% of them either agree or strongly agree that RTs paid fair amount for their work. Very few (37%) of the RTs either agree or strongly agree that RTs are not appreciated for their work. More than 42% of the RTs felt that work assignments are not fully explained (Table: 4.4.5).

Table: 4.4.6 Attitude of respiratory therapists

Characteristic	N = 388
I am Frustrated	
Disagree	138 (36%)
Neutral	117 (30%)
Strongly Disagree	64 (16%)
Agree	46 (12%)
Strongly agree	23 (5.9%)
Happy (I am happy with my career choice)	
Strongly agree	173 (45%)
Agree	154 (40%)
Neutral	44 (11%)
Disagree	12 (3.1%)
Strongly Disagree	5 (1.3%)
Satisfied (My career as an RT is rewarding)	
Agree	160 (41%)
Strongly agree	144 (37%)
Neutral	52 (13%)
Disagree	23 (5.9%)
Strongly Disagree	9 (2.3%)

Table: 4.4.7 Attitude of the respondents based on the genders

Characteristic	Overall, N = 388	Female, N = 238	Male, N = 150	p-value
I am Frustrated				0.7
Agree	46 (12%)	28 (12%)	18 (12%)	
Disagree	138 (36%)	83 (35%)	55 (37%)	
Neutral	117 (30%)	78 (33%)	39 (26%)	
Strongly agree	23 (5.9%)	13 (5.5%)	10 (6.7%)	
Strongly Disagree	64 (16%)	36 (15%)	28 (19%)	
Happy (I am happy with my career choice)				0.8
Agree	154 (40%)	92 (39%)	62 (41%)	
Disagree	12 (3.1%)	6 (2.5%)	6 (4.0%)	
Neutral	44 (11%)	30 (13%)	14 (9.3%)	
Strongly agree	173 (45%)	107 (45%)	66 (44%)	
Strongly Disagree	5 (1.3%)	3 (1.3%)	2 (1.3%)	
Satisfied (My career as an RT is rewarding)				0.9
Agree	160 (41%)	95 (40%)	65 (43%)	
Disagree	23 (5.9%)	15 (6.3%)	8 (5.3%)	
Neutral	52 (13%)	32 (13%)	20 (13%)	
Strongly agree	144 (37%)	89 (37%)	55 (37%)	
Strongly Disagree	9 (2.3%)	7 (2.9%)	2 (1.3%)	

In total, half of the respondents (52%) either disagree or strongly disagree that they were frustrated about their profession (Table 4.4.6). Around 85% of them felt happy and 78% of them satisfied working as a Respiratory Therapist (Table 4.4.7).

Figure: 4.4.2 Radar plot for the faculty survey

The “radar graph” is a promising tool that can be populated with existing data for use in feedback assessment for the faculties. Each axis of this circular radar graph represents one standard statement from our survey. Working group RTs reported lower score in satisfaction and attitude compared to the score in perception (Figure: 4.4.2).

Table: 4.4.8 Factors associated with Respiratory Therapists satisfaction

Variables	AOR	95% CI	P value
Type of Degree (Ref= Masters)	3.18	1.73, 4.98	0.01
Employment status (Ref= full time)	1.98	0.45, 2.88	0.04
Experience (Ref= 11-20 years)	5.77	3.12, 7.21	0.001
Working hours (Ref= <8 hrs)	3.35	2.25, 6.56	0.02
Primary shift (Ref= day)	1.48	0.89, 2.97	0.05
Income (Ref=Above 1,00,000)	4.55	3.78,6.88	0.002

AOR-Adjusted odds ratio; CI-Confident interval

The Respiratory therapists with undergraduate degree were 3.18 times more unsatisfied compared with Masters. Compared with Full time RTs, others were 1.98 times more likely unsatisfied about the employment status. The RTs with less experience were 5.77 times more unsatisfied about the profession and nature of the work. The respiratory therapists who work in shifts other than regular day shift were 1.48 times more likely to be unsatisfied. Respiratory therapists with less income were 4.55 times more unsatisfied about their nature of the job and profession (Table 4.4.8).

CHAPTER: 5

5.0 DISCUSSION

Validation of the tool to assess RT students' perception regarding their career and their learning resources was performed during initial stages of the study, and valuable insights were obtained regarding the Indian RT students' perception regarding the career prospects and level of satisfaction regarding their learning resources through obtaining the response of the students and faculties. Most students are dissatisfied with the practical and theoretical trainings provided, quality of teaching, the available infrastructure available and the skill level of the faculties at their institutions. Given the crucial role that any RTs has, especially the role that RTs play in healthcare delivery, maintenance of appropriate and minimum standards in their training and education is essential. Majority of the respondents (83%) believed that there is no adequate recognition for RTs in India and 90% of the respondents were in fact planning to move overseas seeking job opportunities. Moreover, regarding establishing regulatory body for RTs, 86% of the respondents believe that there is an urgent need to establish a regulatory body. Besides the primary responsibility of defining the scope of the profession (e.g., what procedures RTs can perform and what cannot), the regulatory body shall be accountable for setting requirements for entering and practicing in the profession and shall be an authority to maintain the registry and use the title of respiratory therapist

Respiratory therapy requires high level of competency and therapy the programs require a structured curriculum with perfect balance between theory and clinical application [80]. A study conducted on RT students in the US reported that, the undergraduate RT students' primary goal is

to get graduated and get employed as an active and registered respiratory therapist, with only about 11.5% wanting to do a post-graduation in RT, which implies that they would be interested to gain maximum knowledge from the current RT program in which they are enrolled in through the structured curriculum of the program [81]. Additionally, in a developing country like India, where the field of RT is still emerging, the perception of the students enrolled in the RT programs regarding their future career prospects gains even more significance, as it could have a direct impact on the involvement of the students in the program. The proposed SQ will be a useful tool to measure both, perception of RT students towards their career, and their perception on the available learning resources to enhance their knowledge. The four-factor model of the structured questionnaire (SQ) was performed using structural equation modelling (SEM), by specifying relationships among the observed variables and the unobserved variables [82]. The 27 items SQ would be a valid and reliable scale to measure respiratory therapy students' future carrier perspective and learning resources. The four major domains of the SQ were perception, satisfaction, curriculum and suggestions. On the whole, a higher level of satisfaction towards teaching methodologies, faculties, infrastructure, mode of assessment and curriculum on the whole could be witnessed through the items loaded under the factor's 'satisfaction' and 'curriculum'. However, one of the top priorities that was flagged to be significant was the inadequate recognition of the RTs, in spite of a physically and emotionally challenging work environment.

The structured questionnaire tool thus is the first tool to evaluate the perception of respiratory therapy students towards their future career prospects and satisfaction on the available learning resources. The questionnaire was validated through the response of students enrolled in various respiratory therapy programs across the country, which would be an ideal representative sample of students coming from diverse multicultural and social background. One of the

limitations of the validation study was that, we were unable to compare the findings of the present study with previous research studies as there are no such studies been done using CFA and SEM to validate the SQ among the respiratory therapy students.

Figure: 5.1 A road map to outline the respiratory therapy profession in India

RTs are bedside specialists in respiratory care who combine handling technologically advanced equipment's with their advanced knowledge in respiratory physiology. RTs understand the importance of research and apply evidence-based practice in their everyday practice to ensure better patient-related outcomes [83]. The multiple avenues and domains that RTs work-in demand extensive theoretical as well as practical knowledge in the field, and respondents in the current study believe that they would be able to achieve the same at their current institutions. The respondents were satisfied with the learning resources, infrastructure, academic and practical knowledge of the faculties, and strongly believe that the teaching provided in their respective institutions are of international standards.

Increased professional burnout is reported to be associated with poor job performance, lack of energy, lack of patience, emotional problems, poor communication and listening skills, poorer patient outcomes, and poor attitude towards both patients and colleagues [84, 85]. Majority of respondents in the current study believed that their work is physically and mentally challenging especially in female ($p < 0.05$), which is similar to the burnout at workplace widely reported by RTs across the world [86, 87]. Burnout is primarily associated with three main factors, namely, emotional exhaustion, reduced personal achievement/ accomplishment and depersonalisation [88]. Feeling of reduced personal accomplishment is one of the three important factors involved in burnout. The respondents in the current study perceived that the RTs are not adequately recognised in India. Though the inadequate recognition of RTs in India both from the fellow medical professionals and from the Government of India has been reported previously [11], the perception of inadequate recognition could also be a symbol of burnout mentioned by the RT students, stating that their work is physically and mentally challenging.

The two noteworthy suggestions provided by vast majority of the respondents are to provide career-counselling need to be provided by the University and urgent need to establishing a regulatory body for RT. Around 85% of respondents suggested that career-counselling should be provided by the University/Institution. The suggestion for career counselling could be attributed to two major factors. First, the respondents believe that there is not enough recognition for RTs in India and therefore, a vast majority of them are planning to move abroad for job (90%). Second, nearly 92% of the students' did not have any family members or relatives in the field of respiratory therapy to guide them regarding their future career prospects. The other suggestion put forth by the respiratory therapy students is the urgent requirement to establish a regulatory body for RT in India. There is a quantum leap in the demand from respiratory therapists in India and this has resulted in establishment of increased number of institutions and universities offering respiratory therapy programs in the country with a majority of them running without any regulation or minimum standards of education [42]. A regulatory body in respiratory therapy profession would help safeguard patients' wellbeing and safety by establishing minimum qualification, treatment standards, adequate teaching faculties and a standard curriculum at the teaching institutions [4], which would in turn improve the job opportunities for the RTs in India as well. At present, there is no authorized central or state council that governs respiratory therapy profession in India. This is the major reason for the wide variation in the syllabus and the standard of training seen within the country. The absence of a central authorizing body gives rise to a lack of identity to the profession itself. It is also unfortunate that since the profession is concentrated in the Southern parts of the country, the voice of the RTs as a profession has not been able to attract the attention of the decision-making authorities of the central Government. This has also led to a saturation of

jobs and opportunities in one part of the country with no takers in the rest of the country due to the lack of recognition.

The National Commission for Allied Health Professions (NCAHP) act will be of great benefit to the respiratory therapy community. With the recognition from the government, perhaps a licensing process will exist to improve the profession, multifold. It is expected that the council will unify the entry-level qualification, have a homogenous course duration, uniform curricula, and consistent educational resources. This should also ensure a common structure of available facilities including qualified faculty members for training. Institutes that have so far unscrupulously exploited students in the name of training would be more careful in the future. The new act shall provide immense opportunities for the respiratory therapy educators to design an effective, evidence-based teaching, and assessment strategies in collaboration with the clinical practitioners, thereby helping to prepare the students to transform their education into practice. The roles and responsibilities of the RTs will be standardized along with the training, and perhaps, the scope of practice will increase exponentially. Most importantly, more jobs will be created across the country allowing RTs to work and be of service to the patients. Creating a roadmap is a necessary step toward success of establishing RT as a rewarding profession in India (Figure: 5.1).

Soriana et al., (2020) highlights that the prevalence and impact of chronic respiratory diseases differs in different parts of the world [14]. For instance, the highest prevalence of respiratory diseases is observed in high-income regions, something which has not changed ever since it was first estimated in the year 1990. However, in the middle and low-income regions like south Asia, in spite the crude prevalence being lower than in other regions, the morbidity and mortality (especially premature mortality) attributable to chronic respiratory diseases are highest

in the world. In the past 30 years, Latin America has shown largest progress in alleviating chronic respiratory disease burden.

It is a known fact that there is currently a problem with brain drain affecting respiratory care, nursing, and other professions in India. Indian RTs are especially in high demand in the gulf region. This is good up to a certain level since it brings a good exchange of knowledge. However, financial incentives, higher salaries, retention policies, and establishing a career ladder will help to hold respiratory therapists back in India (Figure:5.1). In 2019, the annual expenditure for the management of chronic respiratory diseases was estimated to be € 380 billion annually among the 28 European Union member states alone [89]. It is certain that RT is an indispensable element of the modern health care system that has enormous potential. Being a billion-dollar healthcare industry, the scope and potential for respiratory therapists is huge. Respiratory therapy could thus be a rewarding profession

5.1 Policy making

The mortality rates due to respiratory diseases are particularly high in south Asia. It is essential that increased attention, resource allocation and appropriate policies are in place to combat the increasing prevalence in the respiratory conditions in the region, which are often neglected when compared to other non-communicable diseases such as diabetes, obesity, cardiovascular disease and cancer [90]. Multiple potential policy solutions do exist which could help in reducing the respiratory disease burden. First and foremost of which is to facilitate early and accurate diagnosis of respiratory conditions through important diagnostic equipment (such as spirometry, radiography equipment, etc.) and such facilities should be provided and made available at the primary health centres level itself (Forum of International respiratory societies, 2017). Next important aspect is to prevent the modifiable risk factors, as most risk factors in chronic respiratory

disorders are preventable. In south Asia, the ambient indoor and outdoor pollution causes a far greater disability than in affluent high-income countries wherein smoking is the main risk factor. However, tobacco smoking, both active and passive, are known to increase risk of chronic respiratory disorders and stringent policies are to be made to prevent tobacco associated respiratory conditions. For example, preventive measures which are something similar to the ones advocated by WHO such as advertising restrictions, creating smoke-free zones, displaying health warning labels on the packaging of tobacco products, increased cigarette taxation and thereby increasing public awareness [5]. Third important aspect involves incorporating new research evidences and strategies associated with respiratory diseases to get optimal outcomes [14].

India, in specific, is in urgent need to make appropriate health policy reforms to combat the fast-increasing prevalence of respiratory conditions to which would suit the needs of over billion people in the country, and work on all three aspects of prevention, diagnosis and management of the various respiratory conditions. The role of RTs in particular would be vital, as they contribute right from prevention, diagnosis, treatment at ICUs and primary health centres, rehabilitation, home care and post-hospitalisation follow up. Appropriate policies and a regulatory body is need of the hour to ensure quality in education for the respiratory therapists students, as we are in the midst of a mushrooming number of institutions in the country. A regulatory body would also oversee the quality of RTs coming out of the institutions and thereby ensure that the patients receive best possible treatment for their respiratory conditions.

In spite of the low pay and low esteem at work place, the faculties held high regards for their profession and were in general happy with their career choice as 85% of them agreed or strongly agreed that they are happy with their career choice. Around 78% of them agreed or strongly agreed that they are satisfied that their career as an RT is rewarding, as 98.7% of

respondents either agreed or strongly agreed that RT is a humanitarian, caring profession. Chronic respiratory diseases often cause persistent and disabling symptoms such as breathlessness, persistent cough, skeletal muscle impairment, general tiredness, exercise limitation leading to difficulty/ inability to perform even otherwise simpler tasks [91]. In addition, respiratory diseases have a psychological impact on the patients, including depression, loneliness and social isolation, impairing the quality of life [92, 93]. Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) is one of the most demanding conditions in an ICU [94]. Dyspnoea, is reported as one of the three most prevalent and distressing physical symptoms, along with pain and thirst, experienced by critically patients in the ICU [95]. The rewarding career of the RTs possibly lies in improving the quality of life and minimising the amount of physical and psychological discomfort encountered by patients with respiratory diseases.

CHAPTER 6

6.0 CONCLUSION

The health-care systems in India have advanced significantly over the years. The COVID-19 pandemic has brought special attention on the respiratory therapy profession as a whole. Due to the revolutionary advances in the diagnostic and therapeutic areas including acute care settings, there has been a quantum leap in the demand for RTs, as they play a crucial role in patient care starting from pre-hospital care, continuing with emergency, and critical care to pulmonary rehabilitation and home care. However, the respiratory therapy students believe that there is no adequate recognition for RTs in India and a vast majority of them want to go abroad seeking job

opportunities immediately after graduation. The lack of recognition remains the major reason why the respiratory therapy students are looking forward to move abroad for job opportunities.

A proper regulatory body for RT would help in standardising both the academic and clinical practice aspects of RT, along with improving job opportunities for respiratory therapists in the future. The standard of the educational institutions delivering the respiratory therapy programs need to be improved to improve overall standard of RT practice in India. When it comes to job satisfaction, a significant relationship exists between experiences that must be read along with the lack of a career ladder. The study findings found no significant association between personal factors and overall job satisfaction. There is an urgent need for establishing a regulatory body to standardise the respiratory therapy programs, quality of the institutions, improve knowledge & skill level of the RTs and in turn improve the standard of care for patients. Knowing the association between personal, occupational factors and job satisfaction could provide several solutions to the healthcare organizations and the respiratory care (RC) department managers to improve job satisfaction levels among their staff, prevent staff turnover and minimize the staff shortage in the RT field, and ultimately the Brain Drain phenomina, causing the migration of talented professionals to other countries. Although many studies investigate job satisfaction in other healthcare professionals, this type of study in the RT field in India is scarce, and job satisfaction levels and associated factors among Indian RTs are still unknown. Further research is needed to understand job satisfaction among Indian RTs and factors that could influence job satisfaction since these studies will increase healthcare organizations' and respiratory care departments' awareness about the job satisfaction of their RT employees.

7.0 STRENGTHS AND LIMITATIONS

- ❖ The current study is the first to validate a structured questionnaire to document the perception of respiratory therapy students and faculties. This could also be considered as a limitation, as we were unable to compare the findings of the present study with previous research studies or any studies having been done using CFA and SEM to validate the SQ among the respiratory therapy students.
- ❖ The subjects were respiratory therapy students from various institutions across the country and therefore the sample could be considered as a true representative sample of the respiratory therapy students in the whole India.
- ❖ Only limited number of representative sample obtained and responded for the study and thus, the findings could not be generalised to RTs throughout the country.
- ❖ The participants' data in this study collected data from various regions in India of RTs. This study's conclusions can only be applied to this group of therapists.
- ❖ The study used an online survey platform and survey that was sent to online groups for participation. Therefore, it is difficult to assure that all participants in this study were RTs. However, the invitation letter clearly stated that this survey was designed for RT participants, and only RT students and RT staff could participate in the survey.
- ❖ Another possible limitation of the current study could be attributed to providing close ended questionnaires to the students, and most of which being to be marked on a 5-pointed Likert scale. Using other qualitative assessment of the subjects might have provided more valuable information and insights on the needs and suggestions of the respiratory therapy students.

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ANNEXURE: QUESTIONNAIRE

ANNEX 1: Ethics Committee Clearance Certificate

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

(PRIVATE UNIVERSITY ESTABLISHED UNDER KARNATAKA STATE ACT NO 42 OF 2013)

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SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY ETHICS COMMITTEE CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE		Date: 02.01.2020
		Ref: SUEC 2020/001
1	Title of the Study	"Establishment Of A Rewarding Profession: Respiratory Therapy In India"
2	Name of the Candidate & Registration No.	Jithin Kalathikudiyil Sreedharan 18SUPHD16 PhD Scholar, College of Allied Health Science Srinivas University
3	Name of the Guide/Co-Guide	Dr Udaya Kumar Rao Professor
4	Decision	The committee here by gives approval of this study in respect of the undertakings contained in the above mentioned project and research instrument(s)
5	Name and Signature of the Chairperson	Dr. Udaya Kumar Rao, Dean Srinivas Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre <i>Udaya Kumar Rao</i>
6	<p>A) Please note that the ethics committee must be informed immediately if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Any material change in the conditions or undertakings mentioned in the application. - Any material breaches of ethical undertaking or events that impact upon the ethical conduct of the research <p>B) The Committee retains the right to withdraw/ amend this ethical clearance certificate if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Any unethical principle or practices are revealed or suspected -Relevant information has been withheld or misrepresented. 	

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ANNEX 2: Declaration and Consent Form (Survey 1)

Respiratory Therapy students' perspectives towards their career and satisfaction about the learning resources.

Nowadays students opinion is considered as a necessary factor to evaluate quality in Universities. This study is performed to evaluate the Respiratory Therapy students perceptions about their career and the satisfaction about the learning resources, and facilities in India.

The questions in this survey is divided into six sections and should take you less than 10 minutes to complete. By clicking the link and completing the survey, you are consenting to participate in this voluntary activity.

Thank you in advance for your participation and support.

*Required

Declaration

As a participant;

- ✓ I am aware that all the participants who will be included in the study would be selected by the investigator based on the expertise.
- ✓ I am aware that I will be asked questions in terms of my personal details and related to my qualification and practice during this study.

Voluntary Participation: I hereby agree that my participation in this study is voluntary and I can withdraw my participation at any time without giving any reason and hence I will not be compensated monetarily for my participation.

Consent from

Investigator/Designee Declaration of Responsibility.

We have explained the nature and objectives of the study in a brief description. We researchers are available for questions and answerable to any queries by the participants.

Support email: jishinkrree@gmail.com

Your participation in this research will be completely confidential and data will be averaged and reported in aggregate, Except in case it is necessary and demanded by the regulatory authorities. There are no risks to individuals participating in this survey beyond those that exist in daily life.

Please print a copy of this consent form for your records, if you so desire.

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1hgBf8uqC2afCRZn8x0STgP3UjP0x86EpW-4Y9uGqSc/edit>

1/18

18/2/22, 18:45

Respiratory Therapy students' perspectives towards their career and satisfaction about the learning resources.

1. You are invited to take part in a research study titled, "Respiratory Therapy students' perspectives towards their career and satisfaction about the learning resources" *

Mark only one oval.

I have read and understand the above consent form, by clicking the next button to enter the survey, I indicate my willingness voluntarily take part in the study.
Skip to question 2

I do not wish to participate in this study

Demographic Data

ANNEX 3 : SURVEY 1 Questionnaire

Survey Questionnaire – Student Survey

Demographic Characteristics	
1	Type of Degree
	Bachelor
	Diploma
	Master
2	Current Academic Year
	Internship
	First year
	Second year
	Third year
3	Age (in years)
	18-20
	20-22
	23-25
	25-30
	Above 30
	Less than 18
4	Gender
	Female
	Male
	Other
5	Marital status
	Married
	Prefer not to say
	Unmarried
6	Annual Income
	< 1 Lakh
	> 6 Lakh
	1-3 Lakh
	4-6 Lakh
7	Type of Family
	Extended Family
	Joint Family
	Nuclear Family
8	Family member or Relative in Respiratory Therapy field
	No
	Yes
9	Enrolment to the program
	Educational loan from the bank
	Fully supported by the family
	Scholarship funded
	Self-funded

10	Do you have plan for moving abroad for Job
	No
	Yes
PERCEPTION	
<i>Answer Type: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly Disagree</i>	
11	RT is a humanitarian, caring profession, where ethical standards of care are maintained
12	RT receives recognition from the community
13	RT are decision makers in Respiratory patient care
14	RT as a profession does not require eligibility criteria (For joining the course)
15	RT profession is equal to other healthcare disciplines
16	I think Respiratory Therapy would be a great profession for my children
17	Demanding work schedule
18	Not enough new graduates to fill increasing number of jobs]
19	Work is physically and emotionally challenging
20	In India, RTs are not recognized enough for their contributions
21	Lack of knowledge about this profession
22	Increased stress on Respiratory Therapists
23	Higher pay for Respiratory Therapists
24	More job choices for presently working Respiratory Therapists
25	Lower quality care for patients
26	Respiratory Therapists will be leaving for other jobs
27	More respect for Respiratory Therapists
28	Improvement in workplace environment
Satisfaction	
<i>Answer Type: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly Disagree</i>	
29	I am Frustrated
30	Happy (I am happy with my career choice)
31	Satisfied (My career as an RT is rewarding)
32	I would recommend RT as a career choice to me immediate family of close friend
33	I feel Respiratory Therapy is similar to the servants job
34	I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do
35	There is really too little chance for promotion on my job
36	When I do a good job, I receive the recognition/appreciation for it that I should receive
37	I sometimes feel my job is meaningless
38	I do not feel that the work I do is appreciated
39	There is too much bickering and fighting at work
40	There are tremendous opportunities for personal growth
41	Work assignments are not fully explained
42	I am satisfied with the career ladder and financial benefits of a Respiratory Therapist
Attitude	
<i>Answer Type: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly Disagree</i>	
43	Low salary and allowances
44	Rewards and incentives
45	Public perceptions of the RT profession
46	Relationship with other disciplines

ANNEX 4: Declaration and Consent Form (Survey 2)

Perceptions, job satisfaction and its impact on career progression among Respiratory Therapists in India.

This study is performed to understand the Indian Respiratory Therapists job perceptions and beliefs about their profession, and its impact on their career progression.

The questions in this survey is divided into Six sections and should take you less than 10 minutes to complete. By clicking the link and completing the survey, you are consenting to participate in this voluntary activity.

Thank you in advance for your participation and support.

*Required

Consent from	<p>Declaration</p> <p>As a participant, ✓ I am aware that all the participants who will be included in the study would be selected by the investigator based on the expertise. ✓ I am aware that I will be asked questions in terms of my personal details and related to my qualification and practice during this study.</p> <p>Voluntary Participation: I hereby agree that my participation in this study is voluntary and I can withdraw my participation at any time without giving any reason and hence I will not be compensated monetarily for my participation.</p> <p>Investigator/Designee Declaration of Responsibility. We have explained the nature and objectives of the study in a brief description. We researchers are available for questions and answerable to any queries by the participants. Support email: jithinksree@gmail.com Your participation in this research will be completely confidential and data will be averaged and reported in aggregate, Except in case it is necessary and demanded by the regulatory authorities. There are no risks to individuals participating in this survey beyond those that exist in daily life.</p> <p>Please print a copy of this consent form for your records, if you so desire.</p>
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https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GgOVH4M5gax1TxGRUR0GdPH-yqJh8ARQgKAmYTIQJw/edit

1/15

0822, 18:50

Perceptions, job satisfaction and its impact on career progression among Respiratory Therapists in India.

1. You are invited to take part in a research study titled, "Respiratory Therapy profession; Perceptions, job satisfaction and its impact on career progression among Respiratory Therapists in India". *

Mark only one oval.

- I have read and understand the above consent form, by clicking the next button to enter the survey, I indicate my willingness voluntarily take part in the study.
Skip to question 2
- I do not wish to participate in this study

Demographic Data

As we seek to balance the representation of different career stages, genders and geographies in the group, we collect relevant data to shortlist candidates within relevant subgroups. We also collect demographic information about other individual characteristics to enable us to monitor the participation and experiences of different groups that Respiratory Therapy profession is open to. Our collection, storage and processing of this data is based on your explicit consent, and you are under no obligation to provide any of this data.

ANNEX 4: SURVEY 2 Questionnaire

Survey Questionnaire: Working RTs

Demographic Characteristics of working RTs	
1	State
	Andhra Pradesh
	I work abroad
	Karnataka
	Kerala
	Maharashtra
	Odisha
	Punjab
	Rajasthan
	Tamil Nadu
	Telangana
	Tripura
	West Bengal
2	Age
	21-30
	31-40
	41-50
	Above 50
	Less than 20
3	Gender
	Female
	Male
4	Married
	No
	Not prefer to say
	Yes
5	Degree
	Bachelor in RT
	Diploma/Advanced Diploma in RT
	Master in RT
	On job training
	PhD/Doctoral
6	Employment Status
	Full time
	Not working
	Part time
7	Role
	Administration
	Bronchoscopy
	Critical care (ICU and ER)

	Education/ Academic Institution (Assistant Professor, Lecturer, Tutor, Demonstrator etc.)
	Entrepreneur
	Hospital setup including (spirometry and advanced spirometry, bronchoscopy, thoracoscopy pulmonary rehabilitation, icu setup and ward setup)
	Non-critical care (ward and long-term)
	Not working
	Outpatient (such as diagnostics and pulmonary rehabilitation)
	Outpatient, non-critical care and critical care.
	PG student
	Private Clinic (rehabilitation centre, home care centre, sleep clinic)
	Pulmonary Rehabilitation freelance
	Pulmonology & critical care
	Respiratory therapist
	Student
	Tutor and Respiratory Therapist
	Work in a medical equipment company
8	Experience
	< one year
	> 20 years
	1-5 years
	11-20 years
	6-10 years
9	Working hours
	< 8 hours
	> 12 hours
	12 hours
	8 hours
10	Primary shift
	24 Hours
	Alternative
	Day
	Night
11	Income
	10,000-20,000
	20,001-30,000
	30,001-40,000
	40,001-60,000
	60,001-100,000
	Above 100,000
	below 10000
Perceptions	
<i>Answer Type: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly Disagree</i>	
12	RT is a humanitarian, caring profession, where ethical standards of care are maintained

13	RT receives recognition from the community
14	RT are decision makers in Respiratory patient care
15	RT as a profession does not require eligibility criteria (For joining the course)
16	RT profession is equal to other healthcare disciplines
17	I think Respiratory Therapy would be a great profession for my children
18	Demanding work schedule]
19	Not enough new graduates to fill increasing number of jobs]
20	Work is physically and emotionally challenging
21	In India, RTs are not recognized enough for their contributions
22	Lack of knowledge about this profession
23	Increased stress on Respiratory Therapists
24	Higher pay for Respiratory Therapists
25	More job choices for presently working Respiratory Therapists
26	Lower quality care for patients
27	Respiratory Therapists will be leaving for other jobs
28	More respect for Respiratory Therapists
29	Improvement in workplace environment
Satisfaction	
<i>Answer Type: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, Strongly Disagree</i>	
30	I feel Respiratory Therapy is similar to the servants job
31	I feel I am being paid a fair amount for the work I do
32	There is really too little chance for promotion on my job
33	When I do a good job, I receive the recognition/appreciation for it that I should receive
34	I sometimes feel my job is meaningless
35	I do not feel that the work I do is appreciated
36	There is too much bickering and fighting at work
37	There are tremendous opportunities for personal growth
38	Work assignments are not fully explained
39	I am satisfied with the career ladder and financial benefits of a Respiratory Therapist
40	I would recommend RT as a career choice to me immediate family of close friend
41	I feel Respiratory Therapy is similar to the servants job
<i>Not applicable, Agree, Disagree, Neutral, Strongly agree, Strongly Disagree Type of answers</i>	
42	Work environment
43	Low salary and allowances
44	Rewards and incentives
45	Public perceptions of the RT profession
46	Relationship with other disciplines
Attitude	
47	I am Frustrated
	Agree
	Disagree
	Neutral
	Strongly agree
	Strongly Disagree

48	Happy (I am happy with my career choice)
	Agree
	Disagree
	Neutral
	Strongly agree
	Strongly Disagree
49	Satisfied (My career as an RT is rewarding)
	Agree
	Disagree
	Neutral
	Strongly agree
	Strongly Disagree

PUBLICATIONS FROM THE THESES

Paper 1: **Validation of a structured questionnaire to assess the perception and satisfaction of respiratory therapy students toward career prospects and learning resources**

Available from: <https://www.cjrt.ca/>

CANADIAN JOURNAL OF RESPIRATORY THERAPY
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Informing the Practice of Respiratory Therapists Globally

Validation of a structured questionnaire to assess the perception and satisfaction of respiratory therapy students toward career prospects and learning resources

Jithin K Sreedharan¹, Udaya Kumar Rao², Mohammed Al Ahmari³, Shashidhar Kotian M⁴, Praveen B Mokshanatha⁵

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Validation of a structured questionnaire to assess the perception and satisfaction of respiratory therapy students toward career prospects and learning resources

ABSTRACT

Background: Respiratory Therapy (RT) is a dignified profession that exists in India since 1995. RT students will play a significant role in strengthening various aspects of healthcare in the future. There are no validated instruments to evaluate students' perceptions of their careers and satisfaction with the learning resources. The primary objective of the current study is to develop and validate a Structured Questionnaire (SQ) for RT students in India, encompassing all the components of their career development and satisfaction.

Methods: Based on the literature review and content validity from RT experts through multiple focused group discussions, reliable SQ was generated with 40 items based on the Likert scale. After getting institutional ethics clearance and informed consent, SQ was administered to 904 RT students across the country. We performed Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) for the global fit. Cronbach's alpha was performed to estimate the internal consistency.

Results: The principal component analysis generated a 4-factor model, and internal consistency for the total scale exceeded the standard criterion of >0.70. Satisfactory goodness of fit data was yielded

PAPER 1: Letter of Acceptance for publication.

Jithin K Sree <jithinksree@gmail.com>

[CJRT] Editor Decision
1 message

Carly Brockington <editor@csrt.com> Mon, Sep 19, 2022 at 5:50 PM
To: JITHIN KALATHIKUDIYIL SREEDHARAN <jithinksree@gmail.com>, Uday Kumar Rao <deanmedical@srinivasgroup.com>, Mohammed Al Ahmari <alahmari87@hotmail.com>, Shashidhar Kotian M <mskot_70@yahoo.co.in>, Praveen Beekannahalli Mokshanatha <bm.praveen@yahoo.co.in>

JITHIN KALATHIKUDIYIL SREEDHARAN, Uday Kumar Rao, Mohammed Al Ahmari, Shashidhar Kotian M, Praveen Beekannahalli Mokshanatha:

Congratulations, your revised paper has been accepted! It has been sent to our publisher, who will contact you with a proof for your approval (look for an email from Danhua from Canadian Science Publishing). It takes her about 2-3 weeks to create the proof. After you return any corrections, it takes about 2-3 weeks until final layout is ready for online publication.

When the paper is ready for publication, we will promote on social media – if you are interested in being tagged, please send me the contacts for you and/or your co-authors or institution (we send it through Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn).

We also offer the chance for authors to create a visual abstract to accompany the media posts, we provide a sample template here. This is optional, but if you want to create something, please send it along to me after you approve the proof.

Let me know if you have any questions throughout this process, and I look forward to getting your paper published. I'll stay in touch, and email me anytime for updates.

Kind regards,

Carly Brockington
Managing Editor
editor@csrt.com

Canadian Journal of Respiratory Therapy

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193K

PAPER 2: Respiratory Therapy Students' Perception toward their Career and Level of Satisfaction with the Learning Resources: A Cross-Sectional Survey Result from India

Name of the Journal: Indian Journal of Respiratory Care (<https://www.ijrc.in/> : Proof copy)

Original Article

Respiratory Therapy Students' Perception toward their Career and Level of Satisfaction with the Learning Resources: A Cross-Sectional Survey Result from India

Jithin K. Sreedharan^{1,2}, Udaya Kumar Rao², Mohammed Al Ahmari³, Shashidhar M. Kotian³, Praveen Beekannahalli Mokshanatha⁴

¹Department of Respiratory Care, Prince Sultan Military College of Health Sciences, Dhahran, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, ²???, Srinivas Institute of Medical Sciences, Srinivas University, ³???, Srinivas University, ⁴???, Institute of Engineering and Technology, Srinivas University, Mukka, Mangaluru, Karnataka, India

Abstract

Background: A structured respiratory care (RC) program has a greater impact on student's critical thinking and problem-solving. Across India, the RC curricula differ in structure and duration. With the exception of a few well-established central universities and autonomous institutions, many required appropriate educational resources and qualified faculty. The objective of the current study is to determine RT students' perception toward their careers and level of satisfaction with the available learning resources. **Materials and Methods:** In this cross-sectional survey, 904 respiratory therapy students participated from medical universities and educational institutions across India. Institutional Ethics clearance was obtained from the host institution and students were given basic information regarding the survey. A validated, structured questionnaire was used which consists of 26 questions that cover four domains: Perception (4 items), satisfaction (13 items), curriculum (5 items), and suggestion (4 items). The questions were answered as per the five-point Likert scale. Data analysis was descriptive, and logistic regression was performed to evaluate factors associated with students' satisfaction with the learning resources. **Results:** The majority of the respondents were female (59%) and belonged (48%) to the age group of <22 years. 92% of them are pursuing bachelor's degree in RC. Most respondents are satisfied with the practical and theoretical training (69%), quality of teaching (70%), the infrastructure available (69%), and the skill level of the faculties (80%) at their institutions. Most respondents (83%) believed that there is no adequate recognition for respiratory therapists (RTs) in India and 90% of the respondents were in fact planning to move overseas to seek job opportunities. Moreover, 86% of respondents believed that there is an urgent need for establishing a regulatory body for the RT profession. **Conclusion:** The respiratory therapy students believe that there is no adequate recognition for RTs in India and a vast majority of them want to go abroad to seek job opportunities. A proper regulatory body for RT would help in standardizing both the academic and clinical aspects of the RT profession, along with improving job opportunities for RTs in the future.

Keywords: Learning resources, respiratory therapy, student's perception, survey

INTRODUCTION

Respiratory therapy is a specialized health-care field, and respiratory therapists (RTs) are operating collaboratively within the multidisciplinary teams in the management of various respiratory conditions. RTs contribute significantly in providing respiratory care (RC) at various levels, such as in the primary health centers, intensive care units, inpatient service at hospitals, preventive health care, and rehabilitation, and also provide with posthospitalization homecare.⁽¹⁾ Knowledge and understanding of the scientific principles, causative cardiopulmonary physiology, and pathophysiology, as well as biomedical engineering and technology adoption, empower RTs to provide patient care services efficiently.⁽²⁾ With increase in the number of both communicable and noncommunicable respiratory conditions and along with the

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PAPER 2: Letter of Acceptance for publication.

Jithin K Sree <jithinksree@gmail.com>

Manuscript Accepted for Publication: ijrc_127_22

1 message

Indian Journal of Respiratory Care <editor@ijrc.in>
To: jithinksree@gmail.com

Thu, Aug 4, 2022 at 10:16 AM

Dear Mr SREEDHARAN,

The Editorial team of Indian Journal of Respiratory Care is pleased to inform you that your manuscript ijrc_127_22 entitled "Respiratory therapy students? perception towards their career and level of satisfaction with the learning resources: A Cross-sectional survey result from India", is accepted for publication in the journal.

We will be sending you page proofs of the manuscript in about 2-3 weeks for final checking and corrections if any., through the manuscript management site before the publication of the manuscript.

Please note that the journal reserves the right to make changes in the language, grammar, presentation, etc. to suit the journal's requirements.

We thank you for submitting your valuable research work to Indian Journal of Respiratory Care.

With warm personal regards,

Yours sincerely,

The Editorial Team

Indian Journal of Respiratory Care

Conference Abstracts from the Theses

Abstract 1

Title: **Respiratory Therapy students' perception towards their career and level of satisfaction with the learning resources- Results of a nationwide survey from India.**

Registration Number: **3774251** (*Abstract will be published in the October 2022, Issue of Respiratory Care Journal*)

Name of the Conference: International Conference of the American Association of Respiratory Care (AARC), 11th November, 2022. New Orleans, USA.

Session: 68th International Respiratory Convention & Exhibition

AARC Open Forum Notification

68th International Respiratory Convention & Exhibition <onbehalf@abstractcentral.com>

Wed 7/27/2022 4:12 PM

To: Jithin Kalathikudiyil Sreedharan <Jithinksree@psmchs.edu.sa>;

Dear Mr. JITHIN SREEDHARAN:

Congratulations! I am pleased to inform you that your abstract (Title: **Respiratory Therapy students' perception towards their career and level of satisfaction with the learning resources- Results of a nationwide survey from India.**, Number: 3774251) has been accepted for presentation at the Open Forum at AARC Congress, to be held November 9–12, 2022 in New Orleans, LA.

Poster Walk Rounds 3
November 11, 2022
3:10 PM - 5:05 PM

I will send more details in the coming weeks to help you with your preparations.

To present at the Open Forum, you are required to register for Congress.

Again, congratulations. I look forward to seeing you in New Orleans.

Dean Hess
Managing Editor
Respiratory Care

Abstract 2

Title: Development and validation of a structured questionnaire to assess the perception and satisfaction of respiratory therapy students toward career prospects and learning resources.

Registration Number: **3771155** (*Abstract will be published in the October 2022, Issue of Respiratory Care Journal*)

Name of the Conference: International Conference of the American Association of Respiratory Care (AARC), 11th November, 2022. New Orleans, USA.

Session: 68th International Respiratory Convention & Exhibition

AARC Open Forum Notification

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Dear Mr. JITHIN SREEDHARAN:

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Poster Walk Rounds 2
November 10, 2022
3:10 PM - 5:05 PM

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Again, congratulations. I look forward to seeing you in New Orleans.

Dean Hess
Managing Editor
Respiratory Care

PUBLICATIONS RELATED TO THE STUDY

Review Paper: Twenty-Five Years of Excellence; Respiratory Therapy in India - Past, Present, and Future

Name of the Journal: Indian Journal of Respiratory Care

Available from: https://www.ijrc.in/temp/IndianJRespirCare915-3791485_103154.pdf

Review Article

Twenty-Five Years of Excellence; Respiratory Therapy in India - Past, Present, and Future

Jithin K. Sreedharan, Sumi Varghese*

Department of Respiratory Care, Prince Sultan Military College of Health Sciences, Dhahran, Dammam, Saudi Arabia, *Department of Respiratory Care, Kasturba Medical College, Mangalore, Karnataka, India

Abstract

Respiratory therapy (RT) profession in India is over 25 years old. Although there have been key advancements in the profession, no history and limited evidence are available about its development and transformation. This article provides a viewpoint on the history and development of the RT field, the evolution of RT education in India, its current state, and the way forward. It also describes in brief the establishment of professional organization, scientific journal, and other major events pertinent to the RT profession in India. This article also emphasizes the need to rationalize the sector and to shape its future to suit the needs of over a billion people who utilize the services of related facilities, directly or indirectly in a highly dynamic healthcare environment. Resolutions to address a few challenges have also been considered, which in our view could be a way forward in this profession. A comprehensive review and assessment was conducted through direct communication, personal interviews, and the review of existing documents in professional organization's archives, representative hospitals, academic institutes, and other relevant texts. The data obtained were evaluated for its relevance and grouped on a thematic basis. This is currently the first paper about the comprehensive history and development of the RT profession in India over the last 25 years.

Keywords: Allied health profession, history, India, profession, respiratory care, respiratory therapy

INTRODUCTION

India's human resources for healthcare services are diverse and multi-faceted.^[1] The term "respiratory care" comprises general assessment of the patient, managing the airways, assisting and managing oxygen supplementation and mechanical ventilation, and administering aerosol medications, bronchial hygiene, chest physiotherapy, pulmonary rehabilitation, home respiratory care, and several additional modalities. These are together applied from the perspective of respiratory physiology and how it develops and disturbs patients.^[2,3] Depending on the healthcare system and clinical setting, these constituents are applied by different professions, including pulmonary physicians, anesthesiologists, intensive care specialists, emergency medical technicians, nurses, physiotherapists, and other allied health professionals.^[4,5] In recent times, this specialized subject area has emerged as a unique career path called "respiratory therapy."^[6,7] The words "interdisciplinary" and "multidisciplinary" further help to define the profession of respiratory care.^[8] The

rapid growth of the population and the concomitant development of healthcare facilities have significantly impacted the progress of RT in India.^[9] The evolution of RT as a specialty has continued during the last two and a half decades. Regardless of the huge demand for services from this sector, the respiratory care domain is still highly fragmented.^[10]

This paper explores the historical developments and phases of growth of the RT profession as well as its future prospects in India. This paper has a special significance as India is celebrating the Silver Jubilee Year of the RT profession in 2020.

Address for correspondence: Mr. Jithin K. Sreedharan, Department of Respiratory Care, Prince Sultan Military College of Health Sciences, P. O. Box 33048, Dammam 31448, Saudi Arabia. E-mail: jthinksree@psmchs.edu.sa

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Correspondence: Quality Improvement in Respiratory Care Education: Implications for Curriculum Change

Name of the Journal: Respiratory Care

Available from: <https://rc.rcjournal.com/content/67/1/154/tab-pdf>

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Quality Improvement in Respiratory Care Education: Implications for Curriculum Change

Jithin K Sreedharan
Respiratory Care January 2022, 67 (1) 154-155; DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4187/respcare.09608>

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Quality Improvement in Respiratory Care Education: Implications for Curriculum Change

To the Editor:

I read the narrative review published by Karlika et al¹ which described, with great enthusiasm, quality management in respiratory care. I see the implications of this review article to be significant, judging from an administrative point of view. The authors explored the development relating to the identification of quality measures as well as their implementation in respiratory therapy departments. They also identified challenges related to their enforcement. In addition, they enumerated the 5 key quality indicators for a respiratory therapy department and the importance of ensuring continuous personnel training in quality measures.

Karlika et al¹ mentioned the relevance of formal training that could have, perhaps, expounded more on it. As a quality leader in a premier undergraduate respiratory care program, I write to share my experiences about the subject and to propose the need for the implementation of methods that assure quality improvement (QI) processes toward an effective respiratory therapy curriculum.

Respiratory care education has become an increasingly important item in the health care agenda, which could be the reason why it has undergone profound transformation and reforms of monumental scale over the past decades, as has been portrayed by Kacmarek et al² in the context of the massive expansion of respiratory therapy education systems, and the associated enhanced participation in the matter, there exist persistent concerns relating to the quality and relevance of preparing the student to evolve as an efficient respiratory therapist. Meanwhile, the standard respiratory therapy curriculum has turned out to be one that steadily gets needed in the reviews of expert respiratory therapy education. What is worrying is that the relevant faculty members seldom get a chance to examine the multidimensional effects that the entire review poses on the established goals of undergraduate education.

In traditional respiratory therapy curricula, QI often received passing mention only. However, in the modern curricula relating to new respiratory therapy programs, QI is incorporated into their clinical and ancillary curricula, to some extent.

It would be judicious for educational institutions to consider training future respiratory therapy professions in QI during their undergraduate studies, with augmentation at postgraduate level through deliberate formal integration into the curricula.³

At present, finding the resources to teach QI during standard respiratory therapy study can be challenging. Perhaps respiratory therapy educators could argue that teaching QI is not necessarily based on prerequisites underpinned by primary importance, or it is impossible to establish in a setting that is characterized by limited space and time to inculcate the core content. My suggestion is that QI lessons should be integrated throughout respiratory care training. Advocating for quality management courses within elective curricula or postgraduate quality management fellowships or certification allows students to gain QI exposure through educational methods other than traditional classroom lessons.

Indeed, QI ought to be introduced as part of the core curriculum content and not merely segregated as a component for consideration within a specialty curriculum. Health care institutions could take advantage of the existing values and quality enhancement tactics, which are usually accustomed to respiratory care practitioners that are actively engaged in clinical QI initiatives. The QI process is vital because it helps to enhance understanding of patient experience and discussions about generally acknowledged QI models as well as demonstrate the resources and systems that health care organizations could employ to respond to this information.⁴ QI learning should be persistently reinforced through such course delivery mechanisms as seminars, projects, and assignments.

My belief in the strength of QI as a means for the advancement of health care infrastructure and respiratory patient care, as well as the fact that it is tangible and practical,⁵ is firm. Integrating QI in the respiratory care curriculum has the potential to expose students to a wider range of opportunities. We must, therefore, see QI apprenticeship not only as a future respiratory therapy domain for clinicians but also one that is essential for professionalized domains of leadership/supervisory roles or those whose functions have a positive association with clinical outcomes in the health care system. Incorporating the QI prospectus within the framework of the rest of the core specialty content to be taught in respiratory therapy would make the associated training more pertinent and would sanction the students to assimilate their learning from innumerable contexts. Undergraduate exposure to QI will help students develop an interest in the topic, understand the significance of working as a team, and enhance future application.

QI could be also anchored by linking it to the performance appraisal of the associated teaching faculty. This is underpinned by the fact that a great educator is one who continuously evaluates the quality of the training that they deliver and also continuously takes measures for QI. Assessment and appraisal of the teaching faculty should consider this as a core element of good practice.⁶ Considering all these advantages of QI in respiratory therapy, I strongly advocate that educational institutions, respiratory therapy schools, and universities integrate QI curricula in their courses relating to undergraduate, postgraduate, and doctoral programs in health care. The merits of QI to novice respiratory therapists should be viewed by its potential to influence frontline health care provider training. The statement of this strategy is predominantly anchored on the active reform of the current respiratory therapy curricula.

Jithin K Sreedharan
Department of Respiratory Care
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Dhahran, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

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1. Karlika M, Sambikumar V, Boman A, Naveed A, Mulla J, Feroze B. Quality management in respiratory care. *Respir Care* 2021;66(9):1485-1494.
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In this issue

Respiratory Care
Vol. 67, Issue 1
1 Jan 2022
Table of Contents
Table of Contents (PDF)
Cover (PDF)
Index by author

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Jump to section

- Article
- Footnotes
- References
- Info & Metrics
- References
- PDF

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154 RESPIRATORY CARE • JANUARY 2022 VOL 67 NO 1

Previous Next

Back to top

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EDITORIAL

Year : 2021 | Volume : 10 | Issue : 2 | Page : 167-168

Fostering quality in respiratory therapy education – A need of the hour

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The respiratory care profession was formally established in India over 25 years ago; concomitantly, numerous training programs were also started in different parts of the country.^[1] Even though these programs started simultaneously, the core curriculum varied in its structure and duration between different institutions. Factors that still need attention to ensure Respiratory Therapist's (RT) quality of education and skills include a uniform nomenclature and good curriculum design, providing qualified faculty and adequate resources.^[2]

Editorial: National Commission for Allied and Health-care Profession: What does it mean for Respiratory Therapy in India?

Name of the Journal: Indian Journal of Respiratory Care

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EDITORIAL

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National commission for allied and health-care profession: What does it mean for respiratory therapy in India?

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REVIEW

Quality assurance in allied healthcare education: A narrative review

Jithin K. Sreedharan¹, Arun Vijay Subbarayalu², Saad M. AlRabeeh³, Manjush Karthika^{1,5,6}, Madhuragauri Shevade^{4,5},
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JK Sreedharan, AV Subbarayalu, Saad M. AlRabeeh, M Karthika, M Shevade, MAA Nasser, AS Alqahtani. Quality assurance in allied healthcare education: A narrative review. *Can J Respir Ther* 2022;58:103–110. doi: 10.29390/cjrt-2022-009.

Introduction: There is no standard methodology for outlining the intricacies of allied healthcare education (AHE) or its quality. The profound misconception is that quality assurance (QA) in AHE is used on a "voluntary" basis. Given the absence of statutory regulatory mechanisms such as accreditation, validation, and audit by the peripheral agencies concerning QA, adoption of QA measures in AHE is not consistent, and it results in producing a subpar allied health workforce. This paper analyzes the need to include QA measures as an essential domain in evaluating the effectiveness of allied health professional education programs.

Method: A large database search was performed using pertinent terms, and a blueprint was developed for a meticulous literature review published between 2015 and 2021. Five hundred eighty-two articles were found and screened; a critical appraisal was performed for 22 peer-reviewed articles for relevant information.

Results: The literature review identified the need to use academic domains such as leadership, planning, delivery, and feedback as QA criteria to evaluate the efficiency of education and training in allied health professional education programs. Instructors and facilitators for specific knowledge and skill development and a description of their roles should also be used in QA evaluation.

Conclusion: Resources for effective learning and teaching in the allied healthcare domain are limited. This review highlights the significant need to include a QA system in AHE, considering the pivotal role of these students in supporting humankind, now and in the future. The findings contribute to the research by providing essential insights into current trends and focusing on existing research in AHE quality.

Key Words: quality assurance; education; allied healthcare profession; allied healthcare education

INTRODUCTION

Allied healthcare is an umbrella term encompassing various healthcare disciplines and supportive services. The professional classification is based on specific practice areas, and it varies among different countries, governmental healthcare bodies, industries, healthcare settings, and training institutions [1]. Allied healthcare professionals (AHPs) diagnose, treat, and rehabilitate patients and conduct disease-prevention activities or healthcare education based on scientific principles and evidence-based measures [2]. The allied healthcare professions include respiratory therapy, radiology, occupational therapy, podiatry, physiotherapy, social work, medical laboratory technology, imaging technology, and other authorized professions that support quality healthcare services to individuals suffering from certain illnesses [1, 2].

The responsibilities of AHPs include the accurate assessment of a patient's health conditions and the provision of appropriate medication and care. However, the healthcare sector is facing specific

challenges, such as failure to address growing consumerism among patients, slow adoption of information technology, workforce shortage, and discontent, which create barriers to providing adequate healthcare services to patients [3]. Standardized assessment procedures and accreditation benchmarks have been set by several international healthcare and quality organizations such as the World Healthcare Organization (WHO), Joint Commission International (JCI), and Global Alliance for Improved Nutrition (GAIN) to lessen the healthcare sector's complexities. These organizations also emphasized the support of allied healthcare services to ensure that quality care is provided to patients. A global survey conducted by the WHO reported that approximately 30% of total health workers are AHPs [4]. Although respiratory therapy, occupational therapy, speech therapy, and physiotherapy are regarded as therapeutically oriented professions, clinical lab and imaging technology professionals are more involved in diagnostic services. The activities in allied healthcare are often interrelated and overlapped role functions are observed as well [5].

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